

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY

MASTER OF DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATION

LINJAY D. ESPINA

SOCIAL ACCEPTABILITY OF TICKET VENDING MACHINES AT THE LIGHT
RAILWAY TRANSIT AMONG PASSENGERS
IN METRO MANILA, PHILIPPINES

Thesis Adviser:

MELINDA DELA PEÑA BANDALARIA, PhD
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

07 June 2023

Permission of the classification of this academic work access is subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations:

Invention (I)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Publication (P)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Confidential (C)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input type="checkbox"/> No
Free (F)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

Student's signature: *Le Espina*

Thesis adviser signature: *Melinda Dela Peña Bandalaria*

University Permission Page

SOCIAL ACCEPTABILITY OF TICKET VENDING MACHINES AT THE LIGHT RAILWAY TRANSIT AMONG PASSENGERS IN METRO MANILA, PHILIPPINES

“I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page.”

“I specifically allow the University to:

Specifically, I grant the following rights to the University:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and in any other databases available on the public internet*
- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing “fair use” of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes.*

 05/17/2024
Linjay D. Espina

Signature over Student Name and Date

Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by LINJAY D. ESPINA with the title: "SOCIAL ACCEPTABILITY OF TICKET VENDING MACHINES AT THE LIGHT RAILWAY TRANSIT AMONG PASSENGERS IN METRO MANILA, PHILIPPINES" is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

MELINDA D. BANDALARIA, PhD
Chair, Thesis Committee

(Date)

BENJAMINA PAULA G. FLOR, PhD
Member, Thesis Committee

(Date)

MELINDA F. LUMANTA, PhD
Member, Thesis Committee

(Date)

DIEGO SILANG S. MARANAN, PhD
Dean
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

06 March 2024

Biographical Sketch

The researcher, Linjay D. Espina was born on 04th of December 1997 in Malabon City. She currently living in Caloocan City with her family. She studied BA in Communication at Adamson University in 2017, and presently studying Master of Development Communication at the University of the Philippines- Open University.

She is currently the Customer Relations Supervisor of Light Rail Manila Corporation (LRMC) who support the day-to-day activities in Operations and oversees the overall feedback mechanism of the LRT-1. In her current employer, she was able to gain different certifications such as: Subject Matter Expert (SME) for Customer Service that was awarded last April 2022, and last June 2023 she was certified as Internal Auditor.

Before she joined the railway industry, she was a Senior Administrative Officer under the supervision of the Undersecretary of Special Concerns in Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) on 2017. She handled International Relations project like BIMP-EAGA (Brunei-Indonesia-Malaysia-Philippines East Asean Growth Area), and local projects for the livelihood of the Filipinos.

Acknowledgement

This research is the result of the efforts of many people to whom the researcher owes part of her future. Thus, she wishes to express his sincerest gratitude for the unwavering support in contributing a great deal to the completion of this study.

To her parents, Adelaida Espina and Earl Escamilla, to all of her family members and friends, for their courage and untiring support.

To the management of Light Rail Manila Corporation for support and assistance. To the Operations, Business Development, and Corporate Communication and Customer Relations Team for showing their support and being very considerate, especially regarding work and school schedules, encouraging the researcher to pursue this study, and providing all the data needed by the researcher.

To the researcher's thesis adviser, Dr. Melinda Bandalaria by providing relevant instructions which had been useful in conducting this study and to her research panel for imparting their knowledge for the improvement of this study, to Dr. Benjamina Flor, and Dr. Melinda Lumanta.

To the researcher's loving and supportive partner, who has given me the strength and wisdom to continue this journey even when I face some difficult times and challenges.

Above all, thanks to the Almighty God, who has given His mercy, compassion, wisdom, and unconditional love on the times that the researchers needed it the most.

Dedication

I would like to dedicate this research to all of the Filipino commuters who are adapting changes for the betterment of Public Transportation in the Philippines. They have given me the drive and discipline to tackle any task with enthusiasm and determination.

I would also like to dedicate this study to Mr. Abdul Nasser Guro and Mr. Vladimir Paraiso who helped me in conceptualizing the whole research and data of the study. They have become my mentors in understanding the railway industry. Without their support, this project would not have been made possible.

I would also like to extend the gratitude and dedication of this study, to all of the Development Communication students and practitioners for never-ending support to communicate with new policies, strategies, and information that would benefit the Filipinos.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	v
Dedication	vi
Table of Contents	vii
List of Tables	ix
List of Figures	x
ABSTRACT	xi
CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION	1
Background of the Study	1
Statement of the Problem	4
Objectives of the Study	4
Hypotheses of the Study	5
Significance of the Study	5
Scope and limitation of the Study	6
Operational definition of terminologies	7
CHAPTER II: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	9
COVID-19	9
Railway Safety Protocol for COVID-19	11
The Regime of Machines	13
Contactless Payment System	15
Ticket Vending Machine (TVM)	17
Consumer Behavior	18
Technophobia	20
Social Acceptability	22
Print Media	23
Theoretical Framework	24
Conceptual Framework	26
Synthesis	28

CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY	29
Research Design	29
Research Locale	30
Technique in Selecting Respondents	30
Description of Respondents	31
Research Instrument	32
Data Gathering Procedure	33
Data Analysis	35
CHAPTER IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	37
Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondents	37
Passenger's Riding Involvement	40
TVM Promotion and Communication Campaign	43
Ticket Vending Machines Encounter	55
Passenger Sentiments	62
CHAPTER V: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION	66
Summary	66
Conclusion	68
Recommendation	69
REFERENCES	73
ANNEXES	
Annex A Convenience Sampling Questionnaire	85
Annex B Survey Poster and On-Ground Survey Photos	86
Annex C Key Informant Interview Questions	87
Annex D Key Informant Interview Photos	90

List of Tables

Table 1 Survey Schedule	34
Table 2 Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents	38
Table 3 Passenger Riding Information	40
Table 4 TVM Promotion Campaign	43
Table 5 TVM Promotion Campaign through Social Media	45
Table 6 TVM Promotion Campaign through Acquaintance (Word of Mouth)	47
Table 7 TVM Promotion Campaign through Onsite Visit (Station Premises)	50
Table 8 Machine Utilization	55
Table 9 Machine Difficulty	57
Table 10 Machine Number of Complaints	61
Table 11 Ticket usage during the Pandemic	62
Table 12 Social Media Posting Schedule	70

List of Figures

Figure 1 Theory of Reasoned Action and Planned Behavior	25
Figure 2 Components of Theory of Reasoned Action and Planned Behavior	26
Figure 3 The Rhetorical Triad	27
Figure 4 Age of Respondents	38
Figure 5 Gender of Respondents	39
Figure 6 Area of Residency	39
Figure 7 Riding Years	41
Figure 8 Riding Intention	41
Figure 9 Commonly used Ticket when riding	42
Figure 10 Mode of Purchase	42
Figure 11 TVM Promotion Tool	43
Figure 12 Ticket Vending Promotion - Social Media Posting	44
Figure 13 Ticket Vending Promotion - On-site Advertisement	49
Figure 14 Advertising Material	50
Figure 15 Branding Guidelines (POL-INT-COM-0002)	52
Figure 16 Ticket Vending Promotion - Printed Posters and Banners	53
Figure 17 Passengers positive feedback towards Ticket Vending Machines	56
Figure 18 Passengers negative feedback towards Ticket Vending Machines	57
Figure 19 SARA Device Social Media Post	59
Figure 20 E-Tap Machine Advertisement	60
Figure 21 Device Utilization Percentage	61
Figure 22 Most used Ticket during Pandemic time	63
Figure 23 TVM Recommendation	64

Abstract

This study investigated and described the concept of today's changes in the public transportation since the riding public have an options to adapt new technologies in line with the digitization or to remain at their accustomed option. The researcher observed that the concept of digitization in the railway industry is not just about the creation and installation of technologies but the readiness of the commuters to accept changes to the advancement of the technologies. The topic of the research was chosen as the relevance on the riding public's curiosity to the introduced technologies in the railway industry to have another option of payment in terms of ticketing and card reloading. Since there are Private Public Partnership (PPP) on the railway lines in Metro Manila and with the fact that it is also operated by different companies, the number of installed Ticket Vending Machines (TVMs) are not equal and determined only based on the passenger flow in a Station.

Consequently, private and public operators of railway lines have their own concepts on how to increase the engagement of technologies to serve the riding public. These companies are competing to retain the market share against other mode of transportation and the loyalty of the commuters. The qualitative approach, specifically in-depth interview and convenience sampling was utilized in this study. This research examined the concept of acceptance of technologies as this can be one of the challenge for the digitization in the Philippines.

Keywords: Digitization; Technology; Railway; Fare and Ticketing; Public Transportation

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Kulash (n.d.) stated that transportation has brought a great impact on the development of social, economic, environmental, and political aspects of the nation. It was able to produce additional funds, the opening possible pathways in the areas, engage with the heads of the states, etc. However, when COVID-19 came and affect the economical aspect of the Philippines, the government needed to execute an immediate plan to avoid physical contact in public transportation (Dela Cruz, 2020).

After three months of lockdown (March to May 2020), the economy of the Philippines needs to be revived. The Philippine government decided to resume partial operations of public transportation and relaxed from Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ) to General Community Quarantine (GCQ). The government imposed to have one-meter distance inside public transportation as experts said that the virus can get if a person touches any surface that possibly caught droplets from a person that is COVID-19 positive and especially when they accidentally rub their eyes, nose, and mouth. Besides Physical Distancing, it is also required to wear a face mask and face shield before boarding any public transportation to lessen the transmission of the virus. (CNN Philippines, 2020; Esmael, 2020)

The World Health Organization (WHO) reminds people to wash their hands for all activities they have done. In the Philippines, to lessen the worry of people, the Bank Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) ordered the banks to decontaminate all deposited cash in Shrink-wrapping machines with the set heat level at the maximum degree temperature (100-150 degrees Celsius) for 20 seconds each part prior transferring in Central banks

(Roberts, 2020; Artida, 2020). However, WHO added that the virus can be indirectly transmitted through objects or any material surfaces used by an infected person since airborne transmission is possible (World Health Organization, 2020). With that, the cashless payment system in tolls or expressways, and railway system are also promoted by the government to decrease the number of a cash transaction that requires personal attendants in ticket booths.

To follow the implemented guidelines of the Department of Transportation (DoTr), LRT-1, LRT-2, and MRT-3 to promote cashless transactions that would aid to lessen the spread of the virus in public transportation. LRT-1 started to be active in terms of health and safety protocol in the Stations. The LRT-1 management proactively advertises the use of a Ticket Vending Machine (TVM) to lessen face-to-face ticket vending (Guzman, 2021). Social media platforms were maximized to inform the LRT-1 passengers about the campaign by using Ticket Vending Machines (TVM). People are already aware of the usage of electronic cards or *beep card* since it was already endorsed by DoTr to the public commuters.

One of the encountered problems by LRT is the acceptance of the new normal in the railway industry. People believed that artificial intelligence, machine learning, and automation should be feared. Most of the jobs might be converted into machines. Their gathered skills and knowledge may become useless as machines can do tasks alone. Robotics can also trigger inequality most especially in the field of customer service. However, some people said that it is more convenient to have detailed information. Another effect of machines on people is the features that might confuse some elderly and people living in far-flung areas as they are not familiar with the features and specifications of the machines found in the city. (Synder, 2019; Ha *et al*, 2011; Bird *et al*, 2020).

According to Navarro and Mckinnon (2020) that in study conducted, the reason why people don't have confidence in the implementation of the programs in the government is due to the terminologies used by the policymakers. They are having a hard time grasping the idea. Considering the mental capacity of the Filipinos in understanding the government's programs, most of the adopted policies are not locally created. Some inputs came from neighboring countries in which some Filipinos think that the foreign country was trying to change the accustomed culture (Gollust, *et al*, 2017).

With that, promoting machine learning to passengers may be challenging. According to Bhattacharya (n.d.), introducing machine learning to customers may affect their behavior in buying and consumption. Consumers may be influenced through available promotional platforms like digital media, traditional media, word of mouth, and other ways to know about machine learning or the product itself. As studied by Syeda *et al* (2021), machine learning during the threat of COVID-19 is being globally practiced. It requires a complex understanding of procedures to at least aid to lessen consumer-facing services. Artificial Intelligence during COVID-19 touches the modernization in every state. Machines were able to run a company or industry to revive the economy.

Statement of the Problem

Since the Light Rail Transit adopted the use of an electronic payment system in 2015, there had been no study about the efficiency of the installed Ticket Vending Machines (TVM) in providing customer service to the passengers. Hence, the study aimed to answer the behavior of the passengers in a machine learning campaign using TVM in LRT.

The researcher's study are guided by the following questions:

1. What does the riding public know about the Ticket Vending Machine?
2. How were Ticket Vending Machines communicated to the riding public?
3. What prevents the riding public to used Ticket Vending Machines?
4. What were the experiences of the passengers in using the Ticket Vending Machines?

Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to find out the efficiency of Machine learning in promoting contactless transactions and the adaptation of the passengers of LRT.

The following are the objectives of the study:

1. Determine what the passengers know about TVM;
2. Describe how the TVM was communicated by the LRT Management to the passengers;
3. Determine the barriers to the use of TVM by passengers; and
4. Recommend a communication strategy that will promote the use of TVM by the passengers.

Hypotheses of the Study

The rapid advancement of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has led to the widespread use of digital interventions in healthcare, education, and even business environments. When pandemic arises, there is an significant increase of the uses of technologies by which researchers are intrigued if people are already in the phase of acceptance of the usage of machines and the readiness in using it.

Learning the technologies could result in manipulating and changing behavior in the human environment. Individuals that utilize technology have a distinct influence on their decision-making process when it comes to business ease and personal objectives.

Significance of the Study

The study on the campaign of determining the social acceptability of adopting new policies and advancements in the railway industry in the Philippines is very convenient and appropriate with the advancements of the technologies. With that, the LRT may have a solution to for the passengers to keep informed about the installed machines in the railway industry.

The findings in the study might help with the following:

Public Commuters- to actively use the Ticket Vending Machines (TVM) inside the Stations. With the current generation, it is convenient to use machines and gadgets.

Philippine Railway Industry- they will be able to capture the sentiments as well as the mindset of public commuters for better promotion of contactless payments. Also,

they can calibrate the advancement of Ticket Vending Machines to make them more user-friendly.

Scientists or innovators- can be benefited from the study to look for any improvements to have passenger-friendly machines.

Society- will learn to accept the innovation and development in public transportation. They can also impart knowledge in the advancement of technologies in the Philippine Railway Industry.

Academic Institution- they will be able to raise the consciousness of the students. They can establish awareness and broaden the concept of modernization. They may have the chance to raise the level of understanding of people in using machines and promote a better railway experience for people.

Future Researchers- may use this study as their reference.

Generally speaking, the campaign for contactless transactions in the railway industry is becoming advanced. Even though there will be no threat of COVID-19 in the whole world, people may still opt to use TVM in the railway industry.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study was conducted at the Light Rail Transit (LRT) with installed Ticket Vending Machines (TVM). Therefore, the researcher is not going to study other railway lines that have do have an installed TVM.

In addition, all data and information collected were came from Key Informants Interviews from the LRT Management, and Convenience sampling from the

passengers. This is to further study the public commuters' preference towards the vending process and the actions taken by the LRT Management in increasing the awareness of the riding public in Ticket Vending Machines.

Operational Definition and Terminology

AI - Artificial Intelligence

APS - Automated Payment System

ECQ - Enhanced Community Quarantine

GCQ - General Community Quarantine

WHO - World Health Organization

BSP - Bank Sentral ng Pilipinas

LRT - Light Rail Transit

MRT - Metro Rail Transit

TVM - Ticket Vending Machine

COVID-19 - CoronaVirus Disease 2019

SARS-CoV - severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus

MERS-CoV - Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus

WFH - Work from home

IATF-EID - Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases

DOTR - Department of Transportation

DOTC - Department of Transportation and Communication

LRTA - Light Rail Transit Authority

AFCS - Automated Fare Collection System

SJT - Single Journey Ticket

PPE - Personal Protective Equipment

CALABARZON - Cavite, Laguna, Batangas, Rizal, Quezon (Philippine Province Region 4-A)

SARA - Stand Alone Retail App

RFID - Radio Frequency Identification

Attitude towards behavior - is the person's perspective on the action.

Behavioral Intention - is the anticipated probability of executing the intended action.

Design Hierarchy - is arranging the elements from least to important information.

Contrast - Differences in objects' sizes, shapes, colors, textures, or any other method can capture the audience's interest;

Layout - It can achieve balance by designing the poster's arrangement in two different ways: symmetrically and asymmetrically.

Perceived Behavioral Control - is described as one's anticipated capacity to move out the requested response.

Phenomenology - is a broad field of research.

Qualitative Research - is a type of phenomenological research that aims to learn more about social phenomena from a perspective. It emphasizes the "why" of cultural trends rather than the "what," and it is based on people's actual experiences as meaning-makers in their daily lives.

Subjective Norm - is the perceived social pressure to do or not engage in the desired behavior.

Typography - it is the text size and style that is used in a poster.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

COVID-19

It was suspected that the outbreak of COVID-19 started in Wuhan, China and the epidemic arise from Hunan Seafood Market where exotic live animals (rats, bats, dogs, snakes, rabbits, etc.) were sold to satisfy the appetite of tourists and customers of wild animals. Until such time, there are reported several cases of pneumonia in the area that took the lives of people who consume foods in the Hunan market. It was lately identified by medical experts as a novel coronavirus that belongs to the family of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV). (Shereen et.al, 2020).

The virus infected countries, globally. The effect of COVID-19 leads to the downfall of the world's economic condition. Due to the strict public health measures, businesses were suspended and the demand for the supply chain decreased. There was also a postponement of domestic and international travel which causes to freeze of the trading system. The impact of crisis affects achieving sustainable economic growth in the world. (Haruhiko, 2020)

According to Duddu (2020), COVID-19 affected the economy of the Philippines. It was reported that the economic growth of the Philippines was weakened by 5.5%. Most of the businesses and establishments did not operate as COVID-19 increased the health risks among the workers. With that, the State of Calamity was declared by the Philippine government and was placed under lockdown. The

Philippines imposed travel restrictions that caused sea, air, and land transportation to stop operating.

In the absence of public transportation, most of the workers are affected and have difficulty showing up to their workplaces. Most of the workers are in need to travel far away from their residences. The commuters suffered and since minimum wage earners are not capable enough to have their service (motorcycle and private vehicles) people are forced to walk or ride bicycles which contributed to their physical and emotional stress. (Suman et al., 2020). With the restrictions on traveling for work, most companies implemented a work-from-home (WFH) scheme. With the guidance of House Bill No. 6152, it is permitted to arrange compressed work schedules for the employees as long as they will complete forty-eight (48) working hours. And, the RA 11165 known as the “Telecommuting Act” where private-sector employees are permitted to work anywhere utilizing computer technologies as an Alternative work arrangement on agreed working hours. With that, the number of workers outside homes is decreasing to allow other employees that require to be physically present in their workplaces. (Amoren *et al*, 2019; Go and Ting, 2017; and Department of Labor and Employment, 2019)

When the government imposed a hard lockdown from March to May 2020, the suffering of Filipinos was visibly noticed by the government. The unpaid bills have accumulated. The rate of unemployed Filipino workers increased due to the declaration of bankruptcy and the lessening of manpower of companies. The government decided to continue the economy of the Philippines by allowing the operation of selected important services and businesses. (Morales and Lema, 2020). According to the Department of Transportation (2020), there is a huge effect of

COVID-19 on the lives of people. The Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) recommended partially opening public transportation like buses and some jeepneys with limited routes to accommodate commuters. This was supported by health and safety protocols like social distancing, wearing of facemasks and face shields, and seat barriers.

Railway Safety Protocol for COVID-19

In providing health and safety protocols, one of the initiatives of the Dutch National Railway is to have a project that can accommodate priority passengers. The passengers are tagged as essential by profession and there are special tickets issued for them. The railway industry also looking forward to experimenting if essential workers can secure their train seats before considering other passengers (Gerstenfeld, 2020).

Globally speaking, the mandatory physical distancing in public transportation has led transportation companies to strictly impose health and safety protocols. The cost to provide alcohol, hand soap, tissues, disinfectant solutions, and availing of UV light for sanitation to avoid the transmission of the virus to the passengers has also increased. Social distancing protocol inside transportation has decreased the sales of transit companies from their regular sales without the pandemic. (Tirachini and Cats, 2020). Whenever passengers are entering the Station's premises and boarding the train, signages for health and safety reminders should be visible. Passenger reminders should be followed to have a safe journey for everyone. Other needed information, as well as updates, must be posted around the Station, and maximize the

use of social media accounts for real-time news. (European Union Agency for Railways, 2020).

In the Philippines, the voices of the minimum wage earners have circulated on social media sites. The government decided to loosen up the quarantine measures to let the workers go back to work. As reported by CNN Philippines (2020), the re-opening of non-essential markets may help to reduce the misery of Filipino workers due to the stricter lockdown. The limited public transportation had lengthened the travel time of the workers because of the long waiting lines to ride public transportation. With that, the Department of Transportation (DOTR) has adjusted the social distancing in railway transit from 1 meter to 0.5 meters, and afterward to 0.3 meters to accommodate more passengers (World Health Organization, 2020).

In compliance with the health and safety protocols, LRT-1 released guidelines to the public. Passengers must undergo a temperature check, those who are higher than 37.6° C, do not wear a facemask and face shields, and those who have symptoms of COVID-19 will not be allowed to ride the train. Disinfecting mats and Alcohols are available inside the LRT-1 premises. Trains are also disinfected using UV light at the end of the line (Baclaran and Roosevelt Stations). (Dela Cruz, 2020)

The Department of Health ensured that the minimum health protocols mandated by the government for riding safely in public transportation are strictly followed. The Department inspected LRT-1 as a confirmation that the company understands the directive. The LRT-1 CEO Juan F. Alfonso explained that the whole line 1 strictly follows the social distancing marks inside the Stations and allows 30% or about 375 passengers to ride the train per way. The railway line religiously reminds the passengers to wear their facemasks, and face shields, and seat or stand only on

the markings inside the train. The company imposed that no talking and no eating be allowed to lessen the spread of the virus (Department of Health, 2020).

To add, in avoidance of person-to-person transactions and the spread of COVID-19, LRT-2 announced that there will be no station tellers to be assigned to ticket booths for ticket vending. The revenue line will maximize the usage of installed Ticket Vending Machines (TVM). Tellers will be only assisting those who are first-time users of the machine. Also, gloves, facemasks, and face shields shall wear during the assistance Marquez (2020).

In MRT-3, the revenue line deployed a total of 30 train marshals to be first responders if there will be emergencies that happened inside the train. They will also serve to remind the passengers about the implemented safety policies of MRT-3. In extending their customer service, train marshals shall take an action against any passenger concerns in the rail operations (Dela Cruz, 2020).

The Regime of Machines

The impact of the pandemic has reached the downfall of some companies that require physical skills. With that, it is observed that the economy is collapsing. People invented machines and technologies to support or operate businesses that have become more useful in generating income. More businesses adapted technologies to save the company from bankruptcy. (Chui *et al*, 2020). According to Soni *et al* (2019) and Naseem *et al* (2020), some companies have switched their strategy from traditional to electronic commerce (e-commerce) in terms of advertising products and services. It can easily influence shoppers or customers to avail of products without

exerting physical effort. People don't need higher education to operate machines it only requires attention.

Artificial Intelligence (IA) has molded fast-paced businesses and industries to have a more efficient and effective marketing strategy. The rise of machines for businesses developed customer satisfaction and customer interaction. The features of the machines attract customers since it is capable contribute to added knowledge of people (Soni *et al*, 2019).

Machine Learning in terms of marketing has increased satisfaction to better customer service. In terms of cost-cutting for manpower and resources, marketing automation was able to save and improve external and internal processes. Technologies, in general, have uplifted the credibility of the company or brand (Mari, 2019).

As observed by Huang and Rust (2020), new technologies give customers a different style of communication through virtual assistants or machine learning chatbots that was able to give an immediate response to queries. IA was also upgraded in terms of encoded vocabulary, most of the machines have translated information into different languages for the convenience of the customers. The in-store machines give better service as it was timely and fully automated.

As studied by Yu *et al* (2017), Artificial Intelligence does not mean disregarding the contribution of humans. The competence of humans to understand some critical procedures of robotics will be needed. It proves that productivity will develop. With the growing population, the needs can be accessed and responded to through AI. Just how the business in the Philippines prepared for digital technology. Most companies

implemented the Work from Home policy to reduce face-to-face interaction and the spread of the virus. In education, classes resume through online and distance learning. Reports and meetings for work are also advantages of machines. In public transportation, machinery was able to enhance the processes and better monitoring of the transport companies (Chua, 2020)

Contactless Payment System

As studied by Franciso, *et al.* (2020), the rise of mobile wallets and other cashless payment systems allows people to transact their bills-payment using their smartphones. It was also easing the burden of carrying cash for security reasons. As defined by Kagan (2020), contactless payment is a digital form of transaction that is commonly used with technologies. Smartcards are the main product; it has built-in chip cards for identification and security purposes. Contactless payments are done through swipe-and-go or tap-and-go schemes in the companies for easier billing and sales.

According to Mezghani (2008), Electronic Ticketing (E-Ticket) was used as a cashless payment system, customers or passengers were able to pay fares, toll fees, and parking fees using contactless cards and mobile phones. Maintaining balance can be done by mobile banking, cash transfers, and loading their cards in the nearest loading station that can accommodate their trip. One of the contactless cards mentioned is the installation of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technologies that are connected to batteries to produce or absorb radio frequency waves that can collect data. E-tickets were able to generate revenues and exact calculation of ridership as well as their estimated time per trip (Ingco *et al.*, 2018).

An Automated Payment System (APS) was proposed to easily track and encode data with regard to the improvement of payment of parking tickets and fares for public transportation. The APS's main objective is to empower the usage of contactless smartcards and mobile phones. The system of APS is aiming for hassle-free payment where queues and long waiting for the customers to pay for tickets will be reduced and introduce an application that can easily be accessed by people. Also, the development of the system will help companies with APS to monitor their sales and profit. (Garcia et al., n.d)

The Department of Transportation and Communication (DOTC) along with the cooperation of the Light Rail Transit Authority (LRTA) developed a project called Automated Fare Collection System (AFCS) intended for LRT 1 & 2 and MRT3. The project's main objective is to replace the magnetic type of ticketing system with a contactless smartcard technology system. For the convenient journey of the passengers or commuters, this project allows them to transfer from one railway to another, and for expansion of the system, this can be also used in other modes of transportation with only one card to be used. The concession agreement for the winning bidder shall be imposed immediately for the advancement of the fare system in the Philippines (Abaya, 2014; Japan International Cooperation Agency, 2018).

The initiative of the Automated Fare Collection System started by establishing a collaboration with AF Payments Inc. that converted all magnetic cards into smartcard. The smartcard is called "Beep". The smartcard can be loadable in Railway Stations by using Kiosks. The Kiosk mentioned was called Ticket Vending Machine (TVM), an automatic machine that can accommodate card load and purchase. Commuters or passengers can buy a Single Journey Ticket (SJT) for one-time boarding or load their beep cards for limitless travel. In response to the usage of new

smartcards, AFCS build automatic gates where passengers can easily tap their cards. The new fare system can easily produce data for monitoring sales and profit (Department of Transportation and Communication & Light Rail Transit Authority, 2012; Kaenzig *et al*, 2019).

The Department of Transportation enforced transit companies to use contactless fare collection. Railway Transportation maximized the use of Ticket Vending Machines to avoid cash handling. With that, e-loading machines were able to dispense tickets and even stored value cards for multiple entries (Department of Transportation, 2020).

Ticket Vending Machines (TVM)

For an efficient ticketing system, Automatic ticket vending machines should issue a ticket to all public transportation for those who will avail of a single ride. The researchers added that ATVM should issue one smartcard that can be also used in other modes of transportation (Sato, *et al.*,2011).

Kumar (n.d) analyzed that Automatic Ticket Vending Machines should have a database of users. The database encoded by the user should be reflected on the smartcard they purchased. The purpose of that is to know the usual destination, travel destination, travel way, and the number of passengers. This could contribute to the security and population count of the country.

As concluded by Athavankar (n.d), ticket vending machines should be passenger-friendly and won't cause long queues at the train stations as it is one of the cheapest transportation that people can afford. The use of ticket vending machines should assist the passenger in a convenient journey. The author added that the

machine must have its proper identification (colors, style of TVM, etc.) and codes on the railway route.

The Automatic Fare Collection System contributed to the development of the urban transport system by upgrading machines and reduction of the usage of coins, tokens, and paper tickets for a fare. The use of smartcards was able to provide additional income to the transport system since they can be circulated rather than producing tickets. (Verougstraete and MacDonagh, 2016).

As reported by Manabat (2015) and, the modern ticketing system was first introduced with LRT-2 in May 2015; MRT-3 in June 2015; and LRT-1 in July 2015 in replacing the magnetic ticketing system. It was described as a tap-and-go technique where passengers can effortlessly ride railway transits with the use of one smartcard that can be loaded from 11 pesos up to a maximum load balance of 10,000 pesos. Card expiration will last up to 4 years from the date of purchase. (Jocson, 2015). Since there is a new production of cash in the Philippines, the ticket vending machine of MRT and LRT was upgraded to accept coins for ticket purchases. With its new design, it can accommodate the new generation of currency coins along with the circulation of old coins. The process took 3 months to develop and deliver (Rey, 2018).

Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior defined by Priest *et al* (2013) refers to the decision-making process of an individual or a group that affects their actions and response. It relates to acquiring goods and services for personal use. As added by Radu (2021), buyer behavior covers the mental and emotional adaptability of people to satisfy their needs and wants.

On the business side, consumer behavior acts as the confirmation of the acceptance and patronage of goods and services. It can create an effective strategy that would attract people to purchase. It has aligned with the proper marketing strategy (Makarewicz, 2013).

Hawkins *et al* (2010) state that to determine the judgment, involvement of consumers in terms of buying their needs, and the product that fits their criteria, there are certain types of behaviors observed. These are (1) Complex buying behavior, which involves purchasing expensive materials or products. Research and feedback are valued for the decision-making process; (2) Dissonance-Reducing buying behavior, it processes the rightful decision-making of the consumer between brands and the worthiness of the product; (3) Habitual buying behavior, the consumer was disregarding the kind of brand of the product as long as it suits on their needs and financial aspects; and, (4) Variety seeking behavior, it is the manner that consumers are after with the mixture of products to formulate self-made results for own contentment (Oke, 2016).

As studied by Qazzafi (2020), there are factors to be considered to determine the decision-making process of buying the consumers, and these are (1) Personal factors that refer to individual characteristics like age and lifestyle, personality, occupation, education, and economic status; (2) Psychological factors that are based on the consciousness of consumer-like beliefs and attitudes, learning, motivation, perception; (3) Social factors that refer on the Interpersonal relationship of a consumer-like family, roles, and status, reference groups; and, (4) Cultural factors that are based on the culture, subculture, and even social class.

With the demand for digital-based consumption, digital market devices have an impact on the way consumers establish a new norm of buying goods and services. New practices are connecting the use of devices and the people, changing the habit and demands. There are also roles that an organization plays, an example of this is the implementation of the device's usage and establishment of the hierarchy of political powers. This concept also corresponds with the ongoing digitalization of the world (Cochoy *et al*, 2020).

With the current trend, the increase in the use of electronics is already adapted by many. It shifted the lifestyles of people as many believed that it is more convenient and practical. People did not notice the impact on the environment. The disposed of materials and parts of the electronics contributed to the e-waste. And, these are hard to decompose and sometimes there are difficulties in recycling due to health concerns risks (Maxwell, 2015).

Technophobia

Technologies carry out an important role to improve processes as well as services. Inventors rely on the needs of the people that could increase their contribution to raising the standard of living. The start of innovations should be seen as a public and private sector achievement. It has to be shared responsibilities and benefits to make it effective. (Shearmur, 2016).

Technological innovation was not a threat to one's culture. In our daily lives, we embrace the advancement of technologies like people with their smartphones, hospitals with health care devices, computers in workplaces, machines in production, etc. It expanded the level of communication in society. (Dickson, 2016). As

researched by Wolnicki and Piasecki (2019), In the 19th century, there was a formulated organization that aims to oppose industrialization. They are called “Luddites”. They believed that skilled workers like them will be replaced by machines and there will be a tendency that they will lose their jobs.

As stated by Nestik et al (2018), anxiety about new technologies is called “technophobia”. This occurs when the person was influenced by their peers. The fear of technology might also adapt through verbal or written communication, and accustomed culture and beliefs. Self-interest also played a big role in the adaptation and acceptance of new technologies.

The lack of knowledge of information technology and access to computers is one of the causes of technophobia. The researcher added that in the Philippine context, poverty contributed to the negative perspective of people toward technology. Computer training, as well as technical assistance, can help to lessen anxiety in science and technology. (Hechanova and Dioquino, 2004). Behavior towards technologies can be changed at any time. Machines made for production cannot be operated without the assistance of experienced workers who are willing to learn procedures. Effectively, machine control has greater effects in terms of producing goods and services for businesses. (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2018)

As observed by Zarina et al (2018) and Giacomo et al, (2019), most of the affected by the fear of technology are people aged 65 and above. Internet access in their time is not available. The skill in computers is not well-developed which could be another reason not to trust their computer skills. Also, people living in far-flung areas do not meet the level of education they needed to obtain technological familiarity. As

studied by Gilbert et al, (2003), Personal interest can lessen technophobia. Which, most inventions nowadays are designed based on individual behavior, intellectual capacity, and common preferences. Technologies are user-friendly that the user may not notice but they are already used every day.

Social Acceptability

As studied by Unde, *et al* (2021), social acceptability is the result of gathered responses from the interaction of an individual or group of communities to a specific plan, proposal, or program that will be executed. Social acceptability may have positive or negative effects depending on the impact on the target areas of implementation.

Al-Saidi (2021) added that social acceptability may build upon the needs of the community. Hence, social attitude and adaption may support the process of providing adequate solutions to social community problems. Every user's interaction with a system not only affects the user's perception of the system but also influences the subjective experience of other people. Whether a machine is perceived as "interesting" or "strange" may have an impact on impression management and consequently the desire to utilize it - even while unaccompanied (Koelle *et al*, 2018).

The research was conducted by Maulidiyanti in 2018 in the railway industry, PT MRT Jakarta understands that every project's success is based on public support and involvement. There is a communication strategy applied by the company, it is defined as a management function that is regularly planned, implemented, and evaluated. It signifies that the Public Relations function and communication strategy have already been integrated into the overall business plan. The communication roadmap that follows the building stage demonstrates this. In other words, the communications program has considered the demands of the organization at every stage of the project.

In line with the public transportation setting, Schlag, *et al* (1997) stated that public transportation pricing was proposed in an attempt to solve road traffic, reduce traveling time, and other road problems that may cause economic delays. Social acceptance was influenced by significant perceptions as it may look like accessibility was intended only for those who pay.

Print Media

According to Emrich (2022), any published document that informs audiences via the use of words and/or visuals is considered print media. The majority of mass media are utilized for promotion and persuasion. Advertising in the media may be for a wide variety of things, including products, services, ideas, people, locations, and events. Each medium has varying capabilities and audiences. Advertisers and advertising agencies evaluate these characteristics and decide where (in which medium) and how (with what frequency) to distribute the message based on the type of messaging and the intended demographic (Premanand, 2012).

Print media such as newspapers, magazines, posters, direct mail, books, and many more are used to increase possible sales and brand awareness through printed communication. One of the used print media considered as out-of-home advertising is posters/billboards, a poster's content must be succinct and engaging to reach an on-the-go person (Picincu, 2021).

According to Girdhar (2020), when creating a poster 6 basic elements should be considered to formulate an effective printed communication: (1) Typography- it is the text size and style that is used in a poster. It must take into consideration the font's clarity, the parts that the audience will concentrate on, and how it is appropriate for the

brand's image; (2) Layout- It can achieve balance by designing the poster's arrangement in two different ways: symmetrically and asymmetrically. While the elements in a symmetric layout are evenly spaced on either of the horizontal axes. While asymmetric is frequently achieved through an uneven distribution of all the constituent parts; (3) Color- It is a smart option to use the brand colors when making a poster for a company. But if you're designing an artistic poster, it's necessary always to try to comprehend how colors connect against one another and what effect they have on the audience; (4) Contrast- Differences in objects' sizes, shapes, colors, textures, or any other method can capture the audience's interest; (5) Design Hierarchy- is arranging the elements from least to important information, and; (6) Shape- Emphasizing the main message by providing a visual path to the audiences.

Theoretical Framework

The study was supported and anchored on the Theory of Reasoned Action and Planned Behavior.

In 1980, the Theory of Reasoned Action was developed to determine an individual's willingness to participate in that behavior at a specific time and location. The concept was created to describe all actions over which humans can exhibit self-control (Hagger, 2019). Behavioral intent is a core pillar of this theory; behavioral intents are controlled by one's attitude about the chances that the activity will produce the intended outcomes, as well as one's subjective assessment of the risks and potential benefits of that outcome.

Figure 1.

Theory of Reasoned Action and Planned Behavior

The variables of the Theory of Reasoned Action and Planned Behavior as elaborated by Zhang (2018), **Attitude towards behavior** is the person's perspective on the action. It is the perceptions and preferences towards a specific behavior. **Subjective Norm** is the perceived social pressure to do or not engage in the desired behavior. While **Perceived Behavioral Control** is described as one's anticipated capacity to move out the requested response.

Behavioral Intention is the anticipated probability of executing the intended action. The following factors influence behavioral intentions: Attitudes towards the behavior (e.g., if participation in the behavior is considered a positive or negative experience), Subjective norms surrounding the practice (e.g., thoughts about whether others believe the same way you do), and Perceived Behavioral Control (e.g., beliefs about one's ability to regulate one's behavior), (Nisson, *et al*, 2016).

As described by Levit and Cismaru (2020), the foundation of successful communication will always start with proper planning and strategy to have a positive outcome. Understanding of the subject matter should come up with illustrations that are easy to understand by many.

Conceptual Framework

The researcher used the Model of the Theory of Reasoned Action and Planned Behavior as a Conceptual Framework to broaden the discussion about the main concept of the Study.

Figure 2.

Components of Theory of Reasoned Action and Planned Behavior

Attitude toward behaviors is the favorable or unfavorable response to the behavior, and values associated with a positive or negative evaluation of an event or action. For example, a regular passenger decides whether what good option in buying ticket is faster and safer way. The passenger will evaluate what could be the best option to purchase ticket based on the feedback gathered from social media or any online platform.

Subjective Norm refers to the peer pressure or social influence on the behavior, the action may vary based on the friends and family's experience and feedback on the behavior. For example, the passenger may act based on the manipulation of the people around him/her. The passenger may push through or

change their mind in terms of the purchase of the ticket based on how the people around them experienced purchasing in the machines.

Perceived Behavioral Control doesn't always allow for people's perceptions of their power to manage their behaviors, there will be no other influence on the decision-making process. For example, the passenger intends to ride the train. He/she may disregard other people's opinion on some processes as long as he/she fulfills his/her expectation (Lezin, n.d; Nguyen, 2020).

To elaborate the discussion properly, the researcher will use the Rhetorical Triangle. According to Aristotle, a speaker's capacity to influence an audience is determined by how well the person speaking communicates. Logos, ethos, and pathos are all used to connect to a certain audience. True transformational world in general, these. Later rhetoricians came up with the term "rhetorical triangle" to describe the relationship between appeals (Taylor, 2021).

Figure 3.

The Rhetorical Triad

With that, Logos (*means the reason/subject*) will be the Buying ticket for riding the train, Ethos (*means the Speaker/communicator*) the Light Railway Transit, and Pathos (*means the belief/audiences*) the passengers.

The researcher believed that the theory presented will be capable of executing positive outcomes in the study. Thus, the theory may also serve as guidance in conducting the study in a short period.

Synthesis

The effect of COVID-19 has given difficulties in the lives of Filipino commuters. Adjustments are made to social distancing from using the PPEs like facemasks and face shields to protect the commuters. With its threat of spreading and the unavailability of some public transportation, it brought impacts on society most especially with the passenger's shift from the new normal. Following Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF) Guidelines and protocols, LRT ensures that they support the lessening of person-to-person contact. They have promoted the use of beep cards for contactless payment in the Stations. The LRT Management also empowers the use of their machines for transactions with the passengers in availing tickets. Thus, the LRT management has noticed that even after the massive campaign of the machines, some passengers failed to comply and most of them are hesitating to use the machines. Later on, they won't ride the LRT. Most of them look for alternative public transportation than use technologies.

With the guidance of the Theory of Reasoned Action and Planned Behavior, the LRT Management may identify the appropriate advertising materials or promotion techniques that will be efficient for the passengers as well as the perceptions of the passengers towards Ticket Vending Machines.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study was focused on Qualitative Research, in a form of the Phenomenology method with the use of an in-depth interview with Key informants and Convenience Sampling.

Qualitative Research is a type of phenomenological research that aims to learn more about social phenomena from a perspective. It emphasizes the "why" of cultural trends rather than the "what," and it is based on people's actual experiences as meaning-makers in their daily lives (University of Texas Arlington Libraries, 2022).

Phenomenology is a broad field of research. In this research methodology, the researcher seeks out data that reveals how people react to an event as well as how they think about it. This approach acknowledges that there is no single absolute standard; simply put, everyone has a unique perspective on things. (Hoover, 2021).

The participants elaborated on the value of the communication process and the behavior of the passengers in accepting the new norms in the railway industry by the use of Ticket Vending Machines. During the pandemic, LRT Management had implemented the use of contactless transactions to lessen the spread of the virus. The study also deepened the understanding of the relationship between the LRT Management and the passengers to support mutual needs like convenience in riding the train.

Research Locale

The study was a thorough interview with Key Informants from LRT Management and the passengers residing in Metro Manila, specifically the LRT passengers.

Metro Manila or *Kalakhang Maynila* has 17 cities that were incorporated in 1975 by a presidential decree to serve as a single administrative region. The capital city of Metro Manila is Manila City, where the center of business, education, culture, economy, and development is located. Metro Manila was approximately 619.6 km² with an increasing population of about 20 million in 2020 (Salita, 2021).

Urban areas like Metro Manila are the fastest place to adapt social implementations for development since it was established to have a higher quality of living than rural areas.

Technique in Selecting Respondents

The researcher would like to know the perspective of the LRT Management and the riding public. With that, the researcher used the Key Informants Interview (KII) for the LRT Management representatives. The representatives came from Operations, Business Development, and Corporate Communications. This is to further investigate the initiatives of the LRT Management in pushing through the contactless transaction. Key informant interviews are in-depth, phenomenological interviews with people who know what has been occurring in their communities. The goal of key informant interviews is to gather information from various persons who have direct knowledge and understanding, such as local leaders, experts, or individuals. The process to identify might provide information about the nature of problems and make solutions for

improvements based on their specific knowledge and understanding (Cossham *et al*, 2019).

On the other hand, the selection of respondents for the riding public was in a convenience sampling wherein the researcher doesn't have a pattern in collecting data. Hence, it will be based on the arriving passengers at the LRT Stations. This is to find out if the passengers were able to follow on new normal in terms of ticket vending amid the threat of COVID-19. Convenience sampling is for those individuals who are easy to access. There is no set method for obtaining these respondents; they might be found by simply asking individuals on the street, in a public facility, or at school. (Edgard *et al*, 2017). With that, the researcher selected respondents subjectively.

Overall, the researcher will be guided by Berlo's SMCR Model of Communication which was defined as an important idea to learn to fully understand the variety of aspects of the communication process as well as the factors that may influence them. It may be used to anticipate and evaluate fundamental communication processes. It has key components: Sender, Message, Channel, and Receiver (Bhasin, 2021).

Description of Respondents

The researcher had an in-depth interview with LRT Management representatives. The following are the participants who were able to deepen the discussion: (a) Operations Manager- tasked to do day-to-day operations in the LRT. Give instructions for a strategy coming from the Management to increase the number of contactless transactions; (b) Business Development Manager- tasked to expand the idea of contactless transactions from rail revenue to non-rail revenue; and (c)

Corporate Communications Head- tasked to establish a communication marketing strategy and handles feedback of the riding public to LRT.

On the other side, Respondents from convenience sampling don't require to have socioeconomic status as long as they ride LRT. The respondents must be willing to participate in the short survey. In addition, the respondents are found in LRT Stations. The researcher understands that the LRT commuters may be in a rush to board the train.

The reason why it needs to have this kind of criterion was due to easily identify the experience, adaptation of the communication process, and changes to the behavior of the passengers to comply with the new norms of the LRT. The study will be effective if the respondents are qualified to answer the following questions that will be asked. The study also provide areas for improvements and recommendations for efficient contactless transactions or ticket vending and marketing strategies that apply to passengers from all walks of life.

Research Instrument

The researcher had a virtual interview with the KII and face-to-face conducted on the short survey to further distinguish the concept of social acceptability of contactless transactions in LRT. In this manner, the researcher had to identify LRT Management representatives and available passengers to answer the survey form.

In the research instrument, the researcher had to categorize the questions to deepen the discussion with key informants: (1) Innovation and Modernization in Railway Industry- it tackles the implementation of a new system in LRT and the knowledge of the passengers about it; (2) Ticket Vending Machine- it tackles the

acceptance or resistance and the limitations of the passengers to use Ticket Vending Machines; (3) Promotion of Contactless Transaction- it elaborates the usefulness of electronic cards to the passenger. It also specifies the communication strategy of LRT Management to increase awareness among the passengers about using Ticket Vending Machines.

The research instrument used for the convenience sampling were divided into five main parts: (1) Profile of the Respondents- will ask basic information to the respondents, (2) Passenger Riding Involvement- it ask the span of experience riding LRT, (3) TVM Promotion and Communication Campaign- it tackles the communication materials and strategies that the passenger have seen in the LRT premises, (4) TVM Encounter- it elaborates the experience of the respondents in using Ticket Vending Machines, and (5) Passenger Sentiments- their feedback about the vending process and development in LRT as a whole.

Overall, the research instrument were able to deepen the discussion between the researcher and the respondents. With that, generating ideas are accommodated to recommend in the process improvement.

Data Gathering Procedure

The gathering for the KII was in a form of face-to-face or virtual interviews. The researcher asked the interviewee a question in which the discussion may start. It was a free-flowing interview. Follow-up questions are asked based on the interviewee's answers. The interviews are recorded for transcribing purposes with the consent of the interviewees.

For convenience sampling, the researcher used a self-administered survey form that is written in *English with Tagalog translation*, to determine the experiences

of the respondents about the research topic. As part of the research protocol and ethics, the researcher must secure the availability and willingness of the respondents to answer the survey. This is to make sure that they are aware of the survey and consented to be part of the study.

The survey lasted for 5 days at different times to ensure that the researcher will not have the same set of respondents. The table no. 1 shows the schedule of the conducted survey onsite and virtual.

Table 1.

Survey Schedule

Day	Time	Location
Monday	8AM-9AM; 11AM-12PM; 4PM-5PM	Pasay City
Tuesday	Virtual Survey	N/A
Wednesday	9AM-10AM; 1PM-2PM; 5PM-6PM	Manila City
Thursday	Virtual Survey	N/A
Friday	10AM-11AM; 12PM-1PM; 2PM-3PM	Quezon City

The survey was a 5–10-minute questionnaire and the respondents are required to show to the researcher the accomplished form. Besides of the survey, the researcher had field notes for any observations about the passenger behavior in the LRT area.

The researcher posted posters strategically where mostly there are passenger queuing to buy a ticket, specifically in Ticket booths and Ticket Vending Machines itself. In addition, to catch the attention of the passengers on queue to answer the form, the researcher gave Gcash Load to 15 lucky respondents using a randomized tool.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed based from the respondents, the interview was transcribed and the survey with the respondents was coded. With that, the researcher was able to collect all inputs without missing any important details. The researcher collated all the answers from the respondents.

The data analysis was anchored on Narrative Analysis. The information gathered from the respondents of KII and Convenience sampling are combined and connected to formulate the result. According to Lumsden (2018), Narrative Analysis is formed and structured from direct experience and perception, as well as the interpretations of some individuals. It also provides useful insight into the diversity of human lives, belief systems, and actions. It also considers the connection between personal experience and larger social and cultural factors. It also entails mutual exploration and significant co-construction between the researcher and the respondents. As added by Allen (2017), Researchers can gather accurate information about their customers using narrative analysis that they cannot even get from other techniques. In qualitative research, narrative analysis uncovers underlying intentions that are difficult to detect directly.

The analysis of the result were deepen since the researcher used Qualitative Coding to specified the needs of the passengers and the actions taken by the LRT Management to respond to the passenger demands. The approach was Inductive coding where specifically the researcher doesn't have a built codebook to follow. It started with the observation of the perspective of the passengers and the LRT Management until the result where a theory is connected. As studied by Yi (2018), When performing intuitive or interpretive research and almost knowing nothing about

the study issue, the inductive coding approach is performed. It's ideal for exploratory studies or when researchers need to identify new hypotheses, notions, or ideas.

.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter discusses the findings and the analysis of the gathered data from the respondents and key informants of the study according to the objectives of the study. The first part describes the profile of the respondents. The second part discusses the passenger's riding involvement. The third part talks about how the TVMs communicate with the passengers. The fourth part talks about the TVM encounter. And lastly, the Passenger sentiments.

The analysis of the interview conducted with key informants and the survey respondents are presented in this chapter. The narrative analysis deepen the discussion using Qualitative coding.

Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table No. 2 summarizes the socio-demographic profile of the LRT Passengers in the conducted survey for 5 days in both onsite and virtual surveys.

Of the 217 respondents, the majority of LRT Passengers were aged 26-35 years old. While ages 46-55 and above 56 years old have the minority of number (Figure 4). Most of the respondents were Female (108) than Male (107) while some respondents don't want to say their gender (2) (Figure 5). The survey also shows that LRT passengers are residing in Metro Manila (157) and some passengers are residing in nearby provinces like CALABARZON (Cavite, Laguna, Batangas, Rizal, and Quezon) and Central Luzon (Aurora, Bataan, Bulacan, Nueva Ecija, Pampanga, Tarlac, and Zambales), and other nearby provinces in Metro Manila (Figure 6).

Table 2.

Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

PROFILE	NO. OF RESPONSE
AGE	
18 years old below	4
18-25 years old	45
26-35 years old	105
36-45 years old	47
46-55 years old	8
above 56 years old	8
GENDER	
Female	108
Male	107
Prefer not to say	2
AREA OF RESIDENCY	
Metro Manila	157
Nearby Provinces (Central Luzon, CALABARZON, etc.)	60

Figure 4.

Age of Respondents

Figure 5.

Gender of Respondents

Figure 6.

Area of Residency

Passenger's Riding Involvement

Table No. 3 shows the riding information of the 217 respondents in the survey which determines the loyalty and train usage of the respondents.

Out of 217 respondents, 72 respondents are riding LRT for about 4-7 years (Figure 7). 165 respondents answered that their riding intention is to go to their respective job areas (Figure 8). About 120 respondents used Stored Value Cards (SVC) for their rides (Figure 9), and 147 respondents preferred to purchase tickets in Ticket booths (Figure 10).

Table 3.

Passenger Riding Information

TRIP INFORMATION	NO. OF RESPONSE
RIDING YEARS	
1-3 years	50
4-7 years	72
8-10 years	39
11-15 years	17
16 years and above	39
RIDING INTENTION	
Work	165
Leisure or Vacation	57
Visit to Relatives	50
School	34
Business	23
Others	12
COMMONLY USED TICKET WHEN RIDING	
Single Journey Ticket (SJT)	97
Stored Value Card (SVC) or Beep Card	120
MODE TO PURCHASE TICKETS	
Ticket booths	147
Ticket Vending Machines	70

Figure 7.

Riding Years

Figure 8.

Riding Intention

Figure 9.

Commonly used Ticket when riding

Figure 10.

Mode of Purchase

TVM Promotion and Communication Campaign

Table No. 4 elaborates on the visibility of the promotion advertisement and the communication for Ticket Vending Machines (TVM) awareness in LRT among the 217 survey respondents.

Table 4.

TVM Promotion Campaign

PROMOTION AWARENESS	NO. OF RESPONSE
TVM PROMOTION TOOL	
Radio	2
Acquaintance (Word of Mouth)	87
Television	32
Print (Newspaper/Journals/Magazine)	13
Social Media	88
Others: Onsite	53
USED ADVERTISING MATERIAL	
Tarpaulin/Banners	27
Social Media Posts	25
Jingle (Song)	0
Freebies/Discounts	11
Signages	9
Service Attendants	20

88 out of 217 respondents mentioned that they learned about the promotion use of TVM through social media (Figure 11) with visibility of advertising materials according to 125 respondents.

Figure 11.

TVM Promotion Tool

As part of the promotion strategy, LRT Management usually posts on social media as part of their content and feature, most especially during the pandemic to avoid direct contact with people. According to LRT Management- Corporate Communication and Customer Relations (KII No. 3) *“We.. it’s part of our hygiene content meaning at least, ‘no, at least once a month, we remind people. And then, there are also special campaigns or efforts not just on our social media, but we tap other media partners or KOLs (Key Opinion Leaders~ influencers), so that, we are not the only ones doing the talking.”*

LRT Management also tapped social media influencers such as Lyqa Maravilla, Macoy Dubs, Uncle Ju, and Joshua Maghirang to spread information about Ticket Vending machines, and contactless transactions. They do also post in the Facebook account about the benefits of contactless payment (Figure 12).

Figure 12.

Ticket Vending Promotion - Social Media Posting

Social Media has the highest rate in terms of TVM promotion, only 24 of the respondents are success convinced to use Ticket Vending Machines for any card transaction. While the remaining 64 respondents still preferred to transact with Ticketbooths. Table No. 5 shows the result of the communication campaign and the hierarchy in terms of the number of respondents.

Table 5.
TVM Promotion Campaign through Social Media

Card Transaction	Common Ticket Used	Age Bracket	No. of Response
Ticket Vending Machines	Stored Value Card	18-25 years old	3
		26-35 years old	14
		36-45 years old	7
Ticket booths	Single Journey Ticket	18-25 years old	14
		26-35 years old	33
		36-45 years old	9
		Others	8

According to the respondents who were convinced to use TVMs, *“Social Media. It explains the proper use of the ticket machines, shows directions or ways how to use it so it's easily to understand. They even use speakers (vloggers, commercial models) and images that guides/explains it's use unlike the tarpaulins and other tools you will have a hard time to understand because no one explains it”* according to Respondent No. 40. As added by Respondent No. 163 *”mas mabilis ang transaction, less contact sa tao at wala ganong pila”*.

Some passengers captured the promotion of TVMs in social media but still preferred using Ticketbooths for any transaction, as mentioned by Respondent No. 38 the reason for patronizing Ticketbooths than TVMs is *”para makabili ng discounted na Beep Card”* and Respondent No. 111 *“mabilis na pag bigay ng ticket”*.

Given the situation, LRT Management strategized posting on their Social Media Accounts like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. They are also studying to capture the interest of the people through Tiktok. As stated by KII No. 3, *“based on our analytics, most of our audience are actively online, late evening. Early evening, around primetime, so, that's one consideration we do whenever we post, so, when people are mostly online, or our audience are online then that's when we post or release these social media posts”*. The TRA explained that the core pillar in the theory of the study is the behavioral intents that there is an subjective assessment of the risks and potential benefits of the outcome. Given with the strategy used by the LRT Management, majority of the passengers are in the phase of attitude towards the behavior and Perceived Behavioral Control wherein they are still opt to queue since it is the accustomed process for buying tickets and reloading their beep cards. According to Salameh et al (2022), there might be a lack of brand knowledge even if the advertisement were posted online, it has an effect with the customer satisfaction

whether they are suitable for the needs of the customer market. It is advisable that the company must advertise in a way that their target market will understand.

Currently, Light Rail Manila Corporation's social media pages have 87, 399 followers on Facebook, 44, 342 followers on Twitter, 558 followers on Instagram, and 6,483 followers on TikTok.

Table 6.

TVM Promotion Campaign through Acquaintance (Word of Mouth)

Card Transaction	Common Ticket Used	Age Bracket	No. of Response
Ticket Vending Machines	Stored Value Card	18-25 years old	9
		26-35 years old	15
		36-45 years old	3
		Others	1
Ticket booths	Stored Value Card	18-25 years old	8
		26-35 years old	29
		36-45 years old	18
		Others	4

The second most used platform is TVM awareness from an Acquaintance or verbal communication with other people. A total of 87 respondents said that they are tried to use TVMs through information came from another person. Most of them are also users of Stored Value cards. On the other hand, Ticket booths are still the preferred convenient way to transact for 59 respondents and 28 are convinced to use TVM. With the theory used in the study, Subjective Norm described as the peer

pressure or social influence on the behavior and the action may vary based on how a person perceived the information to decide if the action will be favorable or not.

The respondents observed that LRT Management has deployed Service Attendants to assist passengers in using Ticket Vending Machines. According to respondent No. 13 *“They are encouraging the people to try the self-service ticket vending machine since you will no longer fall in queue in the ticketing booth if you will reload your cards it is less hassle that way”* that indicates favorability in using TVMs. Respondent No. 75 said *“Sinages and the service attendants also. They guide you on how to use and how to load your beep card using the TVM.”* On the other hand, as mentioned by Respondent No. 85 *“Sinubukan ko lang pero mahirap para sa senior “*. For Respondent No. 209, *“ Minsan po kc sa baclaran walang choice kundi gumamit ng VTM”*

As confirmed by LRT Management- Station Operations Division (KII No. 1) , *“but in terms of the promotion doon sa mga challenges na yon na mayroon to support kung papaano natin mapopromote yung TVM, we actually deployed service ambassadors ‘no that.. Parang.. Who would promote yung machine. So what they do is yung mga pasahero na nakaqueue or even the passengers after inspection area kung ang transaction nila is of course to load or to have this SJT or SVC card, the role of the Service Ambassador is to direct ‘no yung mga pasahero papunta doon sa machine”*. As the LRT Management supports contactless transactions, they have a campaign called #Tap2Ride where the passengers who have enough load in their Beep Cards will skip the purchase process in the Ticket Vending Machines or Ticket booths and go straight into the platforms to ride in the trains.

Figure 13.

Ticket Vending Promotion - On-site Advertisement

According to the study of Swift (2020), the Face-to-Face promotion or marketing has been a successful way in increasing brand awareness since there is an opportunity to build a relationship with the customer as well as creating an memorable experience. It also lessens the distractions around and immediately responds to the passenger's inquiries. As the LRT Management used an on-site advertisement, based on the results of the convenience sampling, the strategy has been effective for capturing the target market and trying to use the TVM as another method of purchasing tickets and reloading their beep cards.

Table 7.

TVM Promotion Campaign through Onsite Visit (Station Premises)

Card Transaction	Common Ticket Used	Age Bracket	No. of Response
Ticket Vending Machines	Stored Value Card	18-25 years old	4
		26-35 years old	12
		36-45 years old	6
Ticketbooths	Single Journey Ticket	18-25 years old	7
		26-35 years old	11
		36-45 years old	8
		Others	5

The table shows that onsite visits or the promotion of Ticket Vending Machines are also visible in the LRT Stations. Based on those who have seen advertising materials in the Stations, Tarpaulin/Banners are the distinguished material in the LRT premises as seen by 27 respondents (Figure 14).

Figure 14.

Advertising Material

As stated by KII No. 3, signages that are posted in the Station have a strategy. LRT Management studied the customer touch points inside the Station, *“so entrance.. perhaps in an area where there is some queuing and then people have a bit more time to stare at the signages and see, no . . . would be the teller booth, kasi you already have there people buying. Also, near the ticket vending machines, ‘no. you have existing people buying single journey tickets . . . We make sure that the signages there are not time sensitive, meaning.. Whether like these signages you can leave even for a year as long as contactless remains a priority of the company”*. As added by KII No. 1, *“we installed also yung mga guide on how to use or navigate yung mga procedures on how to transact doon sa mga machines”*

Every Department in LRT has its responsibilities for promoting TVMs. As mentioned by KII No. 3, they are responsible for messaging and producing advertising materials to be posted on the Stations and social media. *“People are.. most of the time in a hurry, so, as we know and know in transit ads, they shouldn’t be cluttered . . . So, it’s very important that you have very straight forward, easy on the eyes to read, and something that when people take a look at it in one glance, you’ll already know what the signage is saying”*.

LRT Management uses branding guidelines (Figure 15) for any public signages, layouts, colors, text styles, and photographic materials that are usually posted in the Stations and on social media. The frequency of the materials is not time-sensitive as long as the campaign is still being pushed by the Management as mentioned by KII No. 3.

Figure 15.

Branding Guidelines (POL-INT-COM-0002)

The signage posted in the Stations was standardized based on the branding guidelines imposed by the LRT Management. The signage was posted strategically near the TVMs and Station entrances of the Station with appropriate size to catch the attention of the passengers. The materials used were tarpaulins and Sintra boards (Figure 16).

Figure 16.

Ticket Vending Promotion - Printed Posters and Banners

According to Respondent No. 73, as one of the passengers the communication materials posted were able to catch their attention *"nababasa yung banner habang nakapilia"* and Respondent No. 4 *"Thru Facebook (Social Media) and tarpaulins at the station as well. Easy to access and very detailed when it comes to the steps. (Helpful)"*

As studied by Zwygart (2022), print media has been one of the efficient way of advertisement of product and services since it was commonly used ages ago. As years go by, print media were improving based on the strategies that would capture the interest of the target market. Print advertisement was able to give a detailed information and gives the people a feeling with use of creativity. Based on the study, riding public of LRT become aware of the promotion of TVMs with the posted posters and banners, it has an significant impact with the sales of the TVMs as the posted materials are not time sensitive was easy to see by the passengers.

Ticket Vending Machines Encounter

178 over 217 respondents have tried to use Ticket Vending Machines (TVM) as their mode of purchase for LRT tickets (Table No. 8). Of the 178 respondents, 168 of them said described that TVM is a user-friendly machine, and 170 of them purchased and load their beep cards in the machine.

Table 8.

Machine Utilization

MACHINE UTILIZATION		NO. OF RESPONSE
MACHINE USAGE		
Yes		178
No		39
USER FRIENDLY MACHINE		
Yes		168
No		10
MACHINE PURCHASE/RELOAD		
Yes		170
No		8

As described by Respondent No. 22 in terms of its comfortability, *“Some of the reasons why I prefer to use it is that; It is not time consuming. I can have my beep card reload easily”*. Another reason for using it as added by Respondent No. 41 *“Para makaiwas sa mahabang pila”*.

As mentioned by LRT Management- Business Development (KII No. 2) with their observation of passenger behavior towards machines *“.. behavior of people will only be altered if they see something viable. Yung option ay viable. If it’s not available, if it’s not consistent, if it’s not reliable, it will never be considered.”*

Figure 17.

Passengers positive feedback towards Ticket Vending Machines

While 39 respondents who do not wish to use TVM for any card transaction states that most of their reasons are: (1) afraid to make a mistake that would result to machine errors, (2) infrequent riders of LRT, (3) not aware on the machines and its features, and (4) not comfortable reading english instructions. As shared by Respondent 217, *“Di ko alam gamitin kasi nakakasubok lang ako pag pupunta sa Kamag anak”* and Respondent No. 101 *“Natatakot na baka kainin yung binayad ko”*.

With the TRA used in this study, passengers that are not comfortable with the usage of TVM are influenced by the human environment around them and their own experiences. They in the phase of the attitude towards behavior and subjective norm though the intention is still the same but the mode of purchase may be subject for their own assessment since they have already an initial judgement towards TVM.

Table 9.

Machine Difficulty

	MACHINE DIFFICULTY	NO. OF RESPONSE
Yes	MACHINE ERROR	77
No		101

101 of 178 who used TVM for any card transaction did not experience machine error during the process of their purchase (Figure 18) which most of them expect for convenience in their riding journey. On the other hand, some passengers experienced machine errors during their purchases.

Figure 18.

Passengers negative feedback towards Ticket Vending Machines

Passengers shared their complaint and dismay with the machines. As per Respondent No. 12 *“Mas tumatagal at hahaba ang pila”* and Respondent No. 39 *“kinain yung pera at walang lumabas na beep card resibo lang”*. The LRT Management acknowledged that there are still room for improvement and development in terms of TVMs. Currently, the Ticket Vending Machines deployed in the Stations are 7-8 years old already and that was against with the after 5 years upgrading. As mentioned by KII No. 1, *“So, talagang yung TVM in fact parang, on the average currently, nasa 17-18% yung contribution nya. In parang.. doon sa whole transaction ‘no. Lets say for 100, 18 percent yung contribution ng Ticket Vending Machine because yung 28 units is hindi talaga enough para makapag cater ng mga pasahero sa kabuuan... So medyo mabagal na rin sya. And, we also experience yung mga nagiging hard touch na sya especially doon sa screen. May mga pasahero na nakaka experience ng mga naglalag, so that would result doon sa delay of transaction. We experience also doon sa coin hopper issue. So, yun yung mga lumalabas out of service, so ayon. We have ano na, we have parang onboard technician once na maexperience yun ng mga Station, so, they would call ‘no, they would address, the would call report yung issue and the technicians would.. Will rectify yung issue immediately.”*

In response to the complaints received, LRT Management specified that they did some appropriate action to address the problem with the TVMs. The Management is studying to upgrade and add more machines for convenience with their passengers. However, during the pandemic, some of their plans were adjusted due to financial constraints brought by non-operating since the volume of COVID-19 cases is increasing and the government announced lockdowns.

Since the additional and upgrading of the TVM are still in the process of re-planning, one of the initiatives of the LRT Management is to maximize their merchants

in the Station. The Management has installed Stand Alone Retail App (SARA) to accommodate loading on the Beep Cards of the Passengers. Another feature of the initiative is to offer snacks to the passengers with the use of their Beep Card loads, *“The SARA device actually enables them to do more things, Number 1, they can pay or they can do.. they can pay kung gusto nila magsnacks at the same time they can also buy ticket load. Kung kailangan nila ng ticket load or top-up whatever that is. So yun, yun yung mga bagay na nagagawa nila at the same time, Kung wala silang cash, but they have beep credits tapos nagutom sila, they can do or use their credit to pay for their snack can be shawarma or potato corner or whatever that is, yan yung gamit nya. So good form sya, it helps LRMC, it helps the merchant.”* KII No. 2 said.

Figure 19.

SARA Device social media post

The campaign is called #Tap2Pay which was linked to their original campaign #Tap2Ride. Currently, the campaign has 16 participating merchants in the LRT stations. The transactions from the SARA devices cannot still be compared with the transactions done by TVMs and Ticket booths, *“Hindi pa. Actually, ngayon ang best pa rin would be the tellers. And the TVMs, I think.. yung TVM kasi has been there for quite some time, so, mataas na talaga yung adaption rate nya. Pre-pandemic pa lang, may consideration na talaga sya. Yung SARA kasi, it started only I think late last year or only this year yung iba. Marami.. Ah.. pang 18 na yata yung mga ano.. SARA.. And, I really need it to push it more. Even to create awareness, we need to re-direct people to consider this path. We need to guide them with SARA Devices to do your loading and also paying using SARA”* KII No. 2 said.

In addition to reloading kiosks, LRT Management also deployed E-tap Machines. Its features are the same with the Ticket Vending Machine, the only difference is that the E-tap Machine were able to pay bills and top up for gaming apps or even RFIDs.

Figure 20.

E-Tap Machine Advertisement

The study also revealed that the highest number with complaints in terms of service in 2022 was the Ticket Vending Machines. It was followed by Point of Sales (Ticketbooths), and with the least number was the Stand-Alone Retail App (SARA). The complaints were received through LRT’s social media pages, onsite complaints, e-mails / written forms, and hotline. As explained by KII No. 2, *“Tsaka ano ah, tsaka sa totoo lang yung mga tao kasi.. not all of them would still be comfortable for the.. all of the machines, so, yung mga hindi sila gusto mag TVM feeling ko sa paghumaharap sa teller . . .”*

Table 10.

Machine Number of Complaints

Months 2022	POS	TVM	ETAP	SARA
January	1	1	0	0
February	1	1	0	0
March	0	0	0	0
April	0	2	0	0
May	0	0	0	0
June	2	0	0	0
July	0	2	0	0
August	0	1	0	0
September	2	1	0	0
October	0	4	0	0
November	0	1	2	0
December	0	2	0	0
Grand Total	6	15	2	0

Based on the machine utilization average in 2022, it is visibly shown that the Point of Sales (Ticketbooths) has the highest percentage in terms of transactions. While the lowest percentage is the Stand-Alone Retail App (SARA).

Figure 21.

Device Utilization Percentage

TOTAL TRANSACTIONS	Jan-22	Feb-22	Mar-22	Apr-22	May-22	Jun-22	Jul-22	Aug-22	Sep-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	Dec-22	Average YTD
% DEVICE UTILIZATION - TOTAL TRANSACTIONS													
POS	79.1%	78.5%	78.1%	77.0%	72.8%	75.7%	83.0%	83.0%	81.8%	81.9%	81.8%	83.8%	80.1%
TVM	17.3%	18.0%	18.7%	20.2%	24.9%	22.3%	15.0%	15.0%	15.9%	15.7%	15.7%	13.8%	17.4%
ETAP	3.6%	3.4%	3.2%	2.8%	2.1%	1.8%	1.8%	1.8%	2.0%	2.1%	2.2%	2.2%	2.3%
SARA	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

The researcher observed the vending process of Ticketbooths and Ticket Vending Machine in one of the Stations. The Ticketbooths can accommodate 3-4 passengers per minute. Most of the passengers that are on queue are Senior Citizens, Students, and passengers who are with companions. While the Ticket Vending Machine can accommodate maximum of 2 passengers per minute and still depends on the knowledge of the passenger on how to use the machine. The TVMs needs to replenish its tickets and coins once it reached the maximum number of transactions. Most of the passengers that are on queue in TVM are working individuals.

Passenger Sentiments

During the surge of COVID-19 in the Philippines, 119 respondents preferred to use TVMs over traditional face-to-face transactions. Passengers mostly purchase Single Journey Tickets and then reload their Beep Cards.

Table 11.

Ticket usage during the Pandemic

MOST USED TICKET DURING PANDEMIC TIME	
Single Journey Ticket	119
Stored Value Card (SVC) or Beep Card	59
No response	39

Passenger reasons why they preferred buying Single Journey Tickets was due to some restrictions in public transportations. According to Respondent No. 19 “My

beep card is already expired and I seldom ride LRT, since it's pandemic” and Respondent No. 21 “Dahil don ako kumportable dahil madalas ako nakakalimot pag lagay Ng mga gamit at ayaw ko na masayang Ang beepcard ko kaya bumili nalang ako sa tvn Ng single journey ticket para araw araw Di mawala”. As added by Respondent No. 183 “I don't usually go out and ride LRT since classes are online”. Another reason from Respondent No. 214 “Hindi ako masyado umaalis nitong pandemic kaya sayang lang kung bibili ako nung pang matagalan na card”.

On the other hand, those who have use Beep Cards during the surge of Pandemic mentioned that it is more safe to use since no need to touch anything and it is personal use, according to Respondent No. 6. As added by Respondent No. 32 *“kce nga po mas ok n yung beepcard kce ikaw lng yung humahawak keysa s SJT n iba iba yung humahawak”*. Positively, Respondent No. 136 said *“Dahil bawal tayo kung saan saan man humahawak. For safety Social Distancing”*

Figure 22.

Most used Ticket during Pandemic time

Of over 217 respondents, 181 respondents recommend the use of TVM to purchase a ticket in LRT (Figure 23). While 3 respondents didn't agree with TVM's recommendation to LRT Passengers, 33 respondents remain neutral.

Figure 23.

TVM Recommendation

According to respondent no. 5, *“Most of the times there is no queuing, it also helps us to be independent which is the same in other foreign countries transportation terminals and less human contact especially due to the pandemic we have to be careful at all time”*. As added by respondent no. 150 *“It would be much convenient for passengers to have it done by themselves. Though at some cases there are passengers who are not knowledgeable to operate the machine, this will help them accept and slowly cope up that we are innovating. Thru this, we will eliminate the long lines, the waiting time we spent buying and falling in lin in ticket booths. It is great that there are opportunities like this where we can just do it by ourselves.”* In which they positively accept the use of TVM for card loading and purchasing tickets. However, 3 respondents didn't recommend using TVM. Respondent no. 207 stressed that *“hindi*

siya rush hour friendly". 32 respondents remain neutral for the recommendation of TVM, as specified by respondent no. 71, *"Hindi ako masyadong Gumagamit ng TVM kasi walang discount ang Senior"* and respondent no. 112 *"Isang beses ko lang nmn ginamit ung vending kc mas comfortable ako sa ticket booth"*.

There are collaborative efforts to promote machine learning with its passengers as LRT Management explained, *"People take these things differently, people accept these things differently, so, you need to have targeted efforts and at the same time you have to have a plan on how to drive a new behaviors . . . So, in our case, what we did was not only online, but we have to work with different unit or departments internally, so, that you know in the entire customer journey, people are reminded about the campaign, about the benefits of going contactless."* KII No. 3 said.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

This study identified the behavior and the knowledge of the passengers towards the Ticket Vending Machine installed in the Light Railway Transit (LRT). This is also determined the efficiency of the promotion of Ticket Vending Machines in terms of customer service.

1. The researcher conducted a convenience sampling with passengers and majority of the respondents they confirmed that they know the existence of the Ticket Vending Machines and had an experience operating the TVM by purchasing Single Journey Ticket or reloading their Stored Value Cards on a daily basis.
2. In terms of promotion and communication of Ticket Vending Machines, the researcher had conducted a Key Informant Interview with Light Rail Transit Management to know their campaigns and asked the respondents on communication platform they have seen to promote TVMs, the researcher focused on the 3 highest number of response in terms of the advertisement of TVM in different communication platforms. In social media, LRT Management posted creative materials on their accounts, they also tapped Key Opinion Leaders in spreading awareness. The LRT Management also used Word of Mouth by placing Service Ambassadors to guide passengers in using TVMs, it is called Tap2Ride campaign. Strategically, LRT Management also posted printed posters and banners within the Station premises for the passengers to notice.

3. With the results of the conducted convenience sampling, most of the passengers of the Light Railway Transit are infrequent or on budget passengers in which majority of them would like to buy ticket on the daily basis instead of storing their fare in a stored value card. They also expressed their dismay with the machine errors they experienced such as some of the machines were not systematically updated, occurring problems with the acceptance of folded bills or old coins, dispensing change, and delays in the transactions due to frequent errors.
4. Most of the respondents said that the usage of TVM was beneficial, especially when the COVID-19 rose globally. The machine helped to lessen human to human intervention in spreading the virus. Based on the insights of respondents, the TVM machines are only for those who are not in a hurry since it was observed that machines can accommodate a maximum of 2 passengers per minute. Passengers don't need to fall in line for the ticket and they can choose whatever location would like. TVM also contributed to another experience and knowledge in terms of machine usage and lessen the fear in using technology.

Conclusion

With the data gathered, the conclusion in line with the research objectives are presented in this part of the study. The primary goals of the study was to determine and analyze the efficiency of the Ticket Vending Machine at the Light Railway Transit.

1. The researcher determined that the passengers are aware on the existence of the TVMs, and they at least tried to use to test its convenience. However, those passengers who are riding regularly are captured in the different promotions and campaigns made by LRT Management.
2. The researcher described that the promotion of Ticket Vending Machines was communicated with different platforms like social media, word of mouth, onsite advertisement, and so on. The results determined that the LRT Management was able to reach passengers on those platforms. However, the passengers seemed not to adapt to the usage of Ticket Vending Machines as some of them are accustomed to the usual human-to-human vending process given also with the age bracket of the passengers riding LRT.
3. The researcher determined the hindrance to the acceptance of TVMs was due to the experience of riding in public when they first used the machine. The results revealed that the machines are already systematically outdated, lesser quantity installed in the Stations, and frequently malfunctioning.
4. The researcher recommended a communication strategy to increase the number of patronage of Ticket Vending Machine in the Light Railway Transit. The strategy includes the continuous marketing efforts in terms of the posting schedules, messaging, and approach. Subscriptions and system updates are also one of the recommended strategy to lessen the complaints received.

Furthermore, there was a significant difference in terms of the preferences of the passengers and the response of the LRT Management to address the issues.

As studied by Hauslbauer et al (2022), Several psychological phenomena, including momentum, the status quo bias, and the path of least resistance—which is often defined as an inclination to remain the same when not strongly pressured to change—can explain the "decision" not to act. Related causes include cognitive processing constraints, such as feeling overloaded by the quantity and complexity of options, and cognitive misconceptions, such as the belief that a default was chosen for a particular purpose.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendation is hereby suggested for the communication strategy:

Communication Channel

Digital Marketing is one of the most powerful tools for communication nowadays. Thus, it is recommended that LRT regularly post at least once a week about the Ticket Vending Machine Promotion which will serve as a reminder of the existence of the machines in the Stations. In terms of the usage of word of mouth and visual communication, the approach must also be considered based on the dominant age bracket and the characteristics of the passengers. The following can be the sample content of Social Media posts:

Table 12.

Social Media Posting Schedule

WEEK NO.	TOPIC
Week 1, 4, 7, and 10	History of Ticket Vending Machine
Week 2, 6, and 8	Benefits of Ticket Vending Machine
Week 3, 5, and 9	Parts of Ticket Vending Machine

LRT Management can also consider putting advertisements at their customer touchpoints, not just in the Station Entrances and the areas where tickets can be purchased. Ticket Vending Promotions and their benefits can also be communicated inside the trains by putting infographic stickers as well as interactive marketing for the passengers.

Another communication platform that can be tapped is to put a screen inside the train by posting videos in *“How to operate Ticket Vending Machines in Easy Steps.”* In this way, passengers that are on board can have an idea on how the Machine works while waiting to arrive in their destination. To maximize the space in the trains, the LRT-1 Management can also put an informative board that would capture the interest of the passenger since there will be more time to read when on board.

Messaging

Even though the LRT Management has launched initiatives to promote TVMs, some passengers still find it difficult to get used to using the machines. Hence, the messaging of the communication materials must be simple for the passengers to remember, which can be done by creating Jingles, interactive and trendy posts, less formal language, brief information, and digital signages in the Stations themselves. It is also advised to increase the support of social media influencers since the passengers are more active on social media.

Even though the LRT Management had launched campaigns Tap2Ride and Tap2Pay, passengers are not aware on that the campaigns are existing. Hence, it is advisable to sustain the campaign by regularly posting it in social media and create a promo that will urge the passengers to use and reload their cards at the machines that are available in the LRT premises.

On Receivers and Approach

Expand the exposure of the TVM campaign with the non-technology savvy passengers since it was discovered that there is hesitation with the use of the machines by older adults. There must also be an increase in the number of service ambassadors that undergo customer service training that has the perseverance to assist those passengers who want to use TVMs. Upgrading and adding more machines must also be considered since based on the study, few machines available brings inconvenience to some passengers who used the machine for the transactions.

It is also recommended to calibrate in the features of the TVMs the Senior and Student discount to increase the usage of the machines with the individuals who frequently on queue to avail the discounts.

Machine Promotions

Based on the profiling result on the convenience sampling, if there will be a possibility to established new LRT System, monthly or weekly subscription card must be considered as a promotion to those first timers or tourists in Manila. The benchmark for this recommendation is based on the Singapore transportation system using EZ-Link Singapore Tourist cards that can be also use in their Buses and the deposit paid will be refunded upon the return of the card (Eva, 2023).

It is also recommended that the machines will be upgraded in a way that the passengers may swipe their credit or debit cards as another option for payment to promote a more contactless transaction.

REFERENCES

- Abaya, J.E.A. (2014). Establishment of the Program Office for the Automatic Fare Collection Project. Department of Transportation and Communication. <https://dotr.gov.ph/images/issuances/DO/2014/D.O%202014-03.pdf>
- Allen, M. (2017). Narrative Analysis. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781483381411.n368>
- Al-Saidi, M. (2021 March 19). From acceptance snapshots to the Social Acceptability Process: Structuring Knowledge on Attitudes Towards Water Reuse. doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2021.633841
- Amoren, I.A, Cubillan, B.J, Dahipon, P.G, and Tesalona, M. (2019 September 22). Is the Philippine Bureaucracy ready for a work-from-home scheme? <https://www.eropa.co/uploads/8/0/4/8/8048512/117 - amoren et al.pdf>
- Artida, R. (2020 March 26). BSP orders banks to disinfect bank notes. <https://filipinotimes.net/news/2020/03/26/bsp-orders-banks-to-disinfect-bank-notes/>
- Athavankar, U. (n.d). Re-designing Automatic Ticket Vending Machine. <http://www.dsource.in/sites/default/files/case-study/automatic-ticket-vending-machine/introduction/file/ticket-vending-machine.pdf>
- Bhasin, H. (2021 October 18). Berlos Communication Model Explained. <https://www.marketing91.com/berlos-model-of-communication/>
- Bhattacharya, J. (n.d.). 12 Ways to use Machine Learning in Digital Marketing. <https://www.singlegrain.com/artificial-intelligence/12-ways-to-use-machine-learning-in-digital-marketing/>
- Bird, E., Fox-Skelly, J., Jenner, N., Larbey, R., Weitkamp, E., & Winfield, A. (2020 March). The ethics of artificial intelligence: Issues and initiatives. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/634452/EPRS_STU\(2020\)634452_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/634452/EPRS_STU(2020)634452_EN.pdf)

Chua, C.P.B., & Valencia, L.D. (2020 August). The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Education Amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343691393_The_Role_of_Artificial_Intelligence_in_Education_Amidst_of_the_COVID-19_Pandemic

Chui, M., Balakrishnan, T., Hall, B., and Henke, N. (2020 November). Global Survey: The state of AI in 2020. <https://www.mckinsey.com/~media/McKinsey/Business%20Functions/McKinsey%20Analytics/Our%20Insights/Global%20survey%20The%20state%20of%20AI%20in%202020/Global-survey-The-state-of-AI-in-2020.pdf>

CNN Philippines. (2020 June 01). Workers brave Metro Manila roads as PH relaxes COVID-19 lockdown rules. <https://www.cnn.ph/news/2020/6/1/Metro-Manila-GCQ-lockdown-COVID-19.html>

CNN Philippines. (2020 September 11). Gov't approved easing of physical distancing rules in public transport. <https://www.cnnphilippines.com/news/2020/9/11/Public-transportation-physical-distancing-rules-Philippines.html>

Cochoy, F., Licoppe, C., Mclyntre, M.P., and Sörum, N. (2020). Digitalizing consumer society: equipment and devices of digital consumption. DOI: [10.1080/17530350.2019.1702576](https://doi.org/10.1080/17530350.2019.1702576)

Cossham, A. & Johanson, G. (2019 September). The benefits and limitations of using key informants in library and information studies research. <http://informationr.net/ir/24-3/rails/rails1805.html>

Dela Cruz, R.C. (2020 May 08). LRT-1 releases guidelines for resumptions of ops. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1102290>

Dela Cruz, R.C. (2020 May 05). MRT-3 deploys 'train marshals'. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1095689>

Dela Cruz, R. (2020 May 18). LTRFB pushes for cashless payments in public transport. Philippine News Agency. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1103223>

Department of Health. (2020 December 15). Duque: Commuter safety protocols crucial in preventing post-holiday surge. <https://doh.gov.ph/press-release/Duque-Commuter-Safety-Protocols-Crucial-in-Preventing-Post-Holiday-Surge>

Department of Labor and Employment. (2019). Telecommuting Act. <https://www.dole.gov.ph/news/department-order-202-19-implementing-rules-and-regulations-of-republic-act-no-11165-otherwise-known-as-the-telecommuting-act/>

Department of Transportation and Communication & Light Rail Transit Authority. (2012 December 21). PPP for the Automatic Fare Collection System Project for LRT Lines 1&2 and MRT3. Republic of the Philippines, Department of Transportation and Communication & Light Rail Transit Authority. [https://dotr.gov.ph/images/PPP/2012/1.7BContactlessAFCS/Project%20Information%20Memorandum%20\(DP%2012-21-12\).pdf](https://dotr.gov.ph/images/PPP/2012/1.7BContactlessAFCS/Project%20Information%20Memorandum%20(DP%2012-21-12).pdf)

Department of Transportation. (2020 April 26). Protocol/Guidelines for public transport operations. [https://lto.gov.ph/images/Advisory/COVID-19 Transport Protocol v3 +ROAD.pdf](https://lto.gov.ph/images/Advisory/COVID-19%20Transport%20Protocol%20v3%20+ROAD.pdf)

Department of Transportation. (2020). Revolutionizing transportation amid pandemic, 2020 annual report. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1M3i0Xd0asNBAi5QU3haweZbDZZD0mgbZ/view?usp=sharing>

Dickson, M. (2016 June 26). Fears about technology are nothing new. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2016/06/fears-about-technology-are-nothing-new>

Duddu, P. (2020 March 31). Coronavirus in the Philippines: The Covid-19 risk, impact and measures. <https://www.pharmaceutical-technology.com/features/coronavirus-affected-countries-philippines-measures-impact-tourism-economy/>

Edgar, T.W. & Manz, D.O.(2017). Research Methods for Cyber Security. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128053492000042>

Emrich, S. (2022 June 06). The Importance of Print Media and How it can benefit your brand. <https://www.entrepreneur.com/growing-a-business/the-importance-of-print-media-and-how-it-can-benefit-your/426749>

- Esmael, L.K. (2020 December 25). PH Transport sector among hardest hit by Covid pandemic. <https://www.manilatimes.net/2020/12/25/business/business-top/ph-transport-sector-among-hardest-hit-by-covid-pandemic/817266/>
- European Union Agency for Railways. (2020 July 21). COVID-19 Rail Protocol: Recommendations for safe resumption of railway services in Europe. https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/Covid-19-Rail-Protocol_v1.4.pdf
- Eva. (2023 June 08). Singapore Tourist Pass, EZ Link or Contactless Bank Card? Which One is Better?. <https://trevallog.com/singapore-tourist-pass-ez-link-standard-ticket/>
- Francisco, R.J., Reñeses, M.A., and Villar, M. (2020 March). How to be risk-free in using e-payment system. http://www.journalijar.com/uploads/557_IJAR-31003.pdf
- Garcia, C.R, Perez, R., Caraballo, J., Alayon, F., and Padron, G. (n.d). A proposal for a payment system for public transport based on the ubiquitous program paradigm. Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria. <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-208/paper30.pdf>
- Gerstenfeld, M. (2020 July 01). How coronavirus Policy and Environmental Policy Intersect. [doi:10.2307/resrep26356.8](https://doi.org/10.2307/resrep26356.8)
- Giacomo, D.D., Ranieri, J., D'Amico, M., Guerra, F., and Passafiume, D. (2019 September 11). Psychological Barriers to Digital Living in Older Adults: Computer Anxiety as Predictive Mechanism for Technophobia. doi: [10.3390/bs9090096](https://doi.org/10.3390/bs9090096)
- Gilbert, D., Lee-Kelley, L., and Barton, M. (2003). Technophobia, Gender Influences and Consumer Decision Making for Technology-Related Products. <http://www.alternativeminds.co.uk/DG7.pdf>
- Girdhar, A. (2020 December 07). What are the basic elements of poster? <https://www.appypie.com/faqs/what-are-the-basic-elements-of-posters>
- Go, M.O. & Ting, R.S. (2017 August 08). An Act Increasing the normal work hours per day under a compressed work week scheme, amending articles 83, 87, and 91 of Presidential decree no. 442, otherwise as the labor code of the Philippines. https://www.congress.gov.ph/legisdocs/basic_17/CR00345.pdf

- Gollust, S.E., Seymour, J.W., Pany, M.J., Goss, A., Meisel, Z.F., and Grande D. (2017 April 28). Mutual Distrust: Perspectives from Researchers and Policy Makers on the Research to Policy Gap in 2013 and Recommendations for the Future. SAGE Journals. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0046958017705465>
- Guzman, J. E. (2021 January 22). LRT reminds passengers anew to adhere to all safety, health protocols. <https://pia.gov.ph/news/articles/1064628>
- Ha, J.G., Page, T., & Thorsteinsson, G. (2011 June 02). A study of Technophobia and Mobile Device design. DOI: [10.5392/IJoC.2011.7.2.017](https://doi.org/10.5392/IJoC.2011.7.2.017)
- Hagger, M.S. (2019 March 27). The Reasoned Action Approach and the Theories of Reasoned Action and Planned Behavior. <https://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/view/document/obo-9780199828340/obo-9780199828340-0240.xml>
- Haruhiko, K. (2020 October 07). COVID-19 and the Global Economy: Impact and Challenges, *From Asia's perspective*. <https://www.bis.org/review/r201007d.pdf>
- Hauslbauer, A. L., Schade, J., Drexler, C.E., & Petzoldt, T. (2022 March 02). Extending the theory of planned behavior to predict and nudge toward the subscription to a public transport ticket. <https://etrr.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s12544-022-00528-3>
- Hawkins, D.I. & Mothersbaugh, D.L. (2010). Consumer BEHAVIOR Building Marketing Strategy. <https://aclasites.files.wordpress.com/2017/02/consumer-behavior-building-marketing-strategy-11th-edition.pdf>
- Hechanova, R.M. & Dioquino Jr., M.C. (2004). Technophobia and the Filipino Worker. https://pssc.org.ph/wp-content/pssc-archives/Philippine%20Journal%20of%20Psychology/2004/Num%202/07_Technophobia%20and%20the%20Filipino%20Worker.pdf
- Hoover, L. (2021 November 03). 5 Qualitative Research Designs and Research Methods. <https://www.gcu.edu/blog/doctoral-journey/5-qualitative-research-designs-and-research-methods>

- Huang, MH. & Rust, R.T. (2020 November 04). A strategic framework for artificial intelligence in marketing. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11747-020-00749-9>
- Ingco, R.I, Magpantay, M.P, and Malijan, M.H.B. (2018 August 01). PUJ Fare Collection System: An IoT Application. <https://lpulaguna.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/1-PUJ-FARE-COLLECTION-SYSTEM.pdf>
- Japan International Cooperation Agency. (2018 October). Feasibility study on the North South Railway Project- South Line (Commuter) (North-South Commuter Railway Extension Project) in the Republic of the Philippines. https://www.jica.go.jp/english/our_work/social_environmental/id/asia/southeast/p hilippines/c8h0vm0000bk9u4d-att/c8h0vm0000dhvs1p.pdf
- Jocson, M. (2015 March 25). New ticketing system to be used in LRT and MRT this year. <https://untvweb.com/news/new-ticketing-system-to-be-used-in-lrt-and-mrt-this-year/>
- Kaenzig, R., Tiu, J., Mariano, P., and Mettke, C. (2019). Philippine Urban Mobility Programme towards people-first cities empowered by efficient, dignified, and sustainable mobility. https://www.changing-transport.org/wp-content/uploads/2020_Philippine_Urban_Mobility_Programme.pdf
- Kagan, J. (2020 October 10). Contactless Payment. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/contactless-payment.asp>
- Kalayou, MH., Endehabtu, BF., and Tilahun, B. (2020 December 03). The applicability of the Modified Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) on the Sustainable Adoption of eHealth Systems in Resource-Limited Settings. <https://doi.org/10.2147/JMDH.S284973>
- Koelle, M., Boll, S., Olsson, T., and Williamson, J. (2018 April). (Un)Acceptable!?: Re-thinking the Social Acceptability of Emerging Technologies. DOI: [10.1145/3170427.3170620](https://doi.org/10.1145/3170427.3170620)
- Kulash, D.J., (n.d). Transportation and Society. Eno Transportation Foundation. https://safety.fhwa.dot.gov/ped_bike/docs/tph_1.pdf
- Kumar, S. (n.d). Automatic Vending Machine. https://www.academia.edu/23713605/AUTOMATIC_TICKET_VENDING_MACHINE

Levit, T. & Cismaru, M. (2020 June). Marketing social marketing to practitioners. DOI: [10.1007/s12208-020-00245-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12208-020-00245-4)

Lezin, N. (n.d). Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). <http://recapp.etr.org/recapp/index.cfm?fuseaction=pages.TheoriesDetail&PageID=517#footnote2>

Lumsden, K. (2018 May 30). Narratives and Storytelling in Qualitative Research. <https://www.ncrm.ac.uk/training/show.php?article=8252#:~:text=Examples%20of%20narrative%20inquiry%20in,journals%2C%20photographs%20and%20other%20artif%20acts>

Makarewicz, A. (2013 March). Consumer behavior as a fundamental requirement for effective operations of companies. https://www.iois.eu/files/Vol_6_1_Makarewicz.pdf

Manabat, J. (2015 March 25). LRT-2 to get modern ticketing system by May. <https://news.abs-cbn.com/business/03/25/15/lrt-2-get-modern-ticketing-system-may>

Mari, A. (2020 May). The rise of machine learning in marketing: Goal Process, and Benefit of AI-driven Marketing. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332865857_The_Rise_of_Machine_Learning_in_Marketing_Goal_Process_and_Benefit_of_AI-Driven_Marketing

Marquez, C. (2020 July 08). LRTA: No more ticket sellers at LRT-2 stations, tickets only from vending machines. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1303639/no-more-station-tellers-at-lrt-2-tickets-only-available-at-vending-machines-lrta>

Maxwell, R. (2015 September 11). High-tech consumerism, a global catastrophe happening on our watch. <https://theconversation.com/high-tech-consumerism-a-global-catastrophe-happening-on-our-watch-43476>

MBA Knowledge Base. (n.d). Industrial Buying Behavior Models. <https://www.mbaknol.com/industrial-marketing/industrial-buying-behavior-models/>

Mezghani, M. (2008 May). Study on electronic ticketing in public transport. European Metropolitan Transport Authorities. <https://www.emta.com/IMG/pdf/EMTA-Ticketing.pdf>

- Morales, N.J. & Lema, K. (2020 August 03). Philippines fears for economy, income as tough lockdown returns. <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-health-coronavirus-philippines-idUSKBN24Z0D7>
- Maulidiyanti, M. (2018). Communication Strategy for New Public Transport System. [Doi.org/10.18502/kss.v3i11.278](https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v3i11.278)
- Naseem, M., Akhund, R., Arshad, H., and Ibrahim, M.T. (2020 September 30). Exploring the Potential of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning to combat COVID-19 and Existing Opportunities in LMIC: A Scoping Review. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F2150132720963634>
- Navarro, K. and McKinnon, M. (2020). 'Challenges of communicating science: perspectives from the Philippines'. JCOM 19 (01), A03. <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.19010203>.
- Nestik, T., Zhuravlev, A., Patrakov, E., Marianna, S.C., Lioudmila, B., Piurcosky, F.P., and Ferreira, J.V. (2018 November). Technophobia as a cultural and psychological phenomenon: Theoretical Analysis. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328686274_TECHNOPHOBIA_AS_A_CULTURAL_AND_PSYCHOLOGICAL_PHENOMENON_Theoretical_Analysis
- Nguyen, QA., Hens, L., MacAlister, C., Johnson, L., Lebel, B., Tan, SB., Nguyen, HM., Nguyen TN., and Lebel, L. (2018) Theory of Reasoned Action as Framework for Communicating Climate Risk: A Case Study of Schoolchildren in the Mekong Delta in Vietnam. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10062019>
- Nguyen, TD., (2020 August 11). Theory of Planned Behavior as a Theoretical Framework. <https://osf.io/fm9te/download>
- Nisson, C. & Earl, A. (2016). The Theories of Reasoned Action and Planned Behavior: Examining the Reasoned Action Approach to Prediction and Change of Health Behaviors. http://hailab.psych.lsa.umich.edu/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/Nisson-Earl-2015_TRA-TRP-1.pdf
- Picincu, A. (2021 March 30). Print Media Characteristics. <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/print-media-characteristics-43397.html>

- Premanand, M. E. (2012 July). Media Studies- I Print Media. https://www.premclt.com/uploads/9/1/5/9/9159993/media_studies_one.pdf
- Priest, J., Carter, S., and Statt, D.A. (2013). Consumer Behavior. <https://ebs.online.hw.ac.uk/EBS/media/EBS/PDFs/Consumer-Behaviour-Course-Taster.pdf>
- Qazzafi, S. (2020 May 15). Factor affecting consumer buying behavior: A conceptual study. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341407314_Factor_Affecting_Consumer_Buying_Behavior_A_Conceptual_Study
- Radu, V. (2021 May 31). Consumer Behavior. <https://www.omniconvert.com/blog/consumer-behavior-in-marketing-patterns-types-segmentation/>
- Rey, A. (2018 April 17). MRT, LRT ticketing machines now accept new peso coins. <https://www.rappler.com/nation/new-philippine-peso-coins-mrt-lrt-ticket-vending-machines>
- Roberts, M. (2020 May 21). You don't need to worry about spreading the coronavirus with cash. <https://theconversation.com/you-dont-need-to-worry-about-spreading-the-coronavirus-with-cash-137865>
- Salameh, A.A., Ijaz, M., Omar, A.B., Muhammad, H., & Haq, Z.U. (2022 01 July). Impact of Online Advertisement on Customer Satisfaction with the Mediating effect of Brand Knowledge. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.919656/full>
- Salita, D. C. (2021, February 12). Manila. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/place/Manila>
- Sato, Y., Ito, M., and Miyatake, M.(2011). Smartcard ticketing System for More Intelligent Railway. http://www.hitachi.com/rev/pdf/2011/r2011_02a_108.pdf
- Schlag, B. & Teubel, U. (1997 January 01). Public acceptability of transport pricing. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/284543038_Public_acceptability_of_transport_pricing
- Shearmur, R. (2016 July 28). Debating urban technology: technopiles, luddites and citizens, Urban geography. DOI: [10.1080/02723638.2016.1207914](https://doi.org/10.1080/02723638.2016.1207914)

- Shereen, M.A., Khan, S., Kazmi, S., Bashir, N., and Siddique, R. (2020 March). COVID-19 Infection: Origin, transmission, and characteristics of human coronaviruses. [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339970952_COVID-19_infection Origin transmission and characteristics of human coronaviruses](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339970952_COVID-19_infection-Origin-transmission-and-characteristics-of-human-coronaviruses)
- Showkat, N., and Parveen, H. (2017 July). In-depth Interview. [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319162160 In-depth Interview](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319162160_In-depth_Interview)
- Soni, N., Sharma, E.K., Singh, N., and Kapoor, A. (2019). Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Business: from Research, Innovation, Market Deployment to Future Shifts in Business Models. <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1905/1905.02092.pdf>
- Suman, H.K., Agarwal, A., and Bolia, N.B. (2020 June 12). Public Transport Operations After Lockdown: How make it happen? DOI: [10.1007/s41403-020-00121-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s41403-020-00121-x)
- Swift, N. (2020 January 13). The Importance of Face-to-Face Marketing. <https://www.inspiredbusinessmedia.com/the-importance-of-face-to-face-marketing/>
- Syeda, H.B., Syed, M., Sexton, K.W., Syed, S., Begum, S., Syed, F., Prior, F., and Yu Jr. F. (2021 January 11). Role of Machine Learning Techniques to Tackle the COVID-19 Crisis: Systematic Review. DOI: [10.2196/23811](https://doi.org/10.2196/23811)
- Synder, B. (2019 March 07). Our Misplaced Fear of Job-Stealing Robots. <https://www.gsb.stanford.edu/insights/misplaced-fear-job-stealing-robots>
- Taylor, D. (2021 October 10). Rhetorical Triangle: Definition & Example. <https://study.com/academy/lesson/rhetorical-triangle-definition-example.html>
- Tirachini, A. & Cats, O. (2020 July). COVID-19 and Public Transportation: Current assessment, prospects, and research needs. [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342573493_COVID-19 and Public Transportation Current Assessment Prospects and Research Needs](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342573493_COVID-19_and_Public_Transportation_Current_Assessment_Prospects_and_Research_Needs)
- Uhde, A. & Hassenzahl, M. (2021 March 15). Towards a better understanding of Social Acceptability. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2103.01637.pdf>

United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. (2018). Technology and Innovation Report 2018: Harnessing Frontier Technologies for Sustainable Development. https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/tir2018_en.pdf

University of Texas Arlington Libraries. (2022 April 13). Quantitative and Qualitative Research. https://libguides.uta.edu/quantitative_and_qualitative_research/qual#:~:text=Qualitative%20research%20is%20a%20process,in%20their%20every%20day%20lives.

Verougstraete, M. & MacDonagh, M. (2016 February). Automatic Fare Collection System: The Case of Manila. <https://www.unescap.org/sites/default/d8files/Case%206-%20Automated%20Fare%20Collection.pdf>

Wolnicki, M & Piasecki, R. (2019 August 09). The New Luddite Scare: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Labor, Capital and Business competition between US and China. <https://doi.org/10.2478/joim-2019-0007>

World Health Organization. (2020 September 15). Philippines Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) situation report #53. www.who-phl-sitrep-53-covid-19-15september2020.pdf

World Health Organization. (2020 March 29). Modes of transmission of virus causing COVID-19: implications for IPC precaution recommendation. <https://www.who.int/news-room/commentaries/detail/modes-of-transmission-of-virus-causing-covid-19-implications-for-ipc-precaution-recommendations>

Yi, E. (2018 July 24). Themes Don't Just Emerge — Coding the Qualitative Data. <https://medium.com/@projectux/themes-dont-just-emerge-coding-the-qualitative-data-95aff874fdce>

Yu, D.K., Cororaton, C., Ilao, J., Cheng, C., Aviso, K., Cayamanda, C., Promentilla, M.A., Atienza, R., Infante, R., and Tan, R. (2017). Policy Brief: Artificial Intelligence and its Potential Adverse Impacts on Philippine Economy. https://dlsu-aki.weebly.com/uploads/1/0/2/2/102266760/11232017_policy_brief_artificial_for_printing.pdf

Zarina, I., Circenis, K., and Ertis, R. (2018). Measuring the technophobia among middle-aged and older adults in Latvia: A pilot study. https://www.shs-conferences.org/articles/shsconf/pdf/2018/12/shsconf_shw2016_02003.pdf

Zhang, K. (2018 May 28). Theory of Planned Behavior: Origins, Development and Future Direction. [http://www.ijhssi.org/papers/vol7\(5\)/Version-4/K0705047683.pdf](http://www.ijhssi.org/papers/vol7(5)/Version-4/K0705047683.pdf)

Zwygart, M. (2022 April 11). Is print advertising still effective in 2022?. <https://coppmedia.com/is-print-advertising-effective/>

ANNEXES

ANNEX A

CONVENIENCE SAMPLING QUESTIONNAIRE

Survey Link:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSc4mWm1vm15_SnvsGGQi8UpsdMI_BDHIAgdulLJMIXDc9Tzq/viewform

SOCIAL ACCEPTABILITY OF TICKET VENDING MACHINES AT THE LIGHT RAILWAY TRANSIT DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC AMONG PASSENGERS IN METRO MANILA, PHILIPPINES

Dear Respondents,

I am Linjay Espina, a student from the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU) conducting a study on the Social Acceptability of Ticket Vending Machines (TVM) installed at the Light Railway Transit during the COVID-19 Pandemic among passenger in Metro Manila, Philippines.

In line with this, I would like to seek for your consent to use your answers in the study to determine the communication strategy in promoting contactless transaction in response to COVID-19 in Light Railway Transit.

Here is the link to the Google form to participate in the survey:

Please take note that your participation is completely voluntary, and you may choose to decline or stop at any moment in the survey process.

Rest assured that all data collected will remain confidential and will only be used for this study. The results of this study will be recorded, will be analyzed, and will be included in the thesis manuscript of the researcher. The data will be kept/stored securely and deleted after the customary 3-5 years in storage.

Please answer the questions on the survey as completely and honestly as you can.

It should take approximately 10-20 minutes to complete.

(The raffle will be done on September 11, 2022. Kindly put your contact details so we can send you a message if you win)

ldespina@up.edu.ph [Switch account](#)

Not shared

* Indicates required question

I agree and volunteered to participate in the Survey: *

(Ako ay boluntaryong sumasang ayon survey na ito)

Yes

No

ANNEX B

SURVEY POSTER AND ON GROUND SURVEY PHOTOS

CALL FOR SURVEY RESPONDENTS

You are invited to participate to our research:
"Social Acceptability Of Ticket Vending Machines at the Light Railway Transit during the Covid-19 Pandemic among passengers in Metro Manila, Philippines"

REQUIREMENT:
-LRT-1 PASSENGER AT ANY AGE

SCAN HERE:

15 Lucky Respondents WILL BE RANDOMLY SELECTED TO RECEIVE:

- 5 Respondents 200 GCASH LOAD
- 10 Respondents 100 GCASH LOAD

TERMS AND CONDITIONS

- The raffle draw will be on **September 11, 2022**.
- Only those who have completely accomplished the form will be eligible for the raffle.
- Contact details cannot be re-used. The entry will be invalid.
- Winners will receive a text message & email for confirmation and instructions to claim.
- The researcher will use a randomizer tool to determine the winner.
- This promotion is not connected with Light Rail Manila Corporation and this is purely for academic purposes only.
- For inquiries and concerns, you may send an email to: ldespina@up.edu.ph.

ANNEX C

KEY INFORMANT INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Corporate Communications

1. In your own perspective, what does the contactless transaction means?
2. How does LRT-1/LRMC support the contactless transaction initiatives in the railway industry in the Philippines?
3. During the pandemic time, how does the LRT-1 ensure that contactless transaction using TVM is safer than the usual vending process in Ticket booths?
4. How do you promote Machine Learning to your passengers?
5. What is the role of Corporate Communication in terms of promotion of Ticket Vending Machine?
6. What is your strategy in posting publicly the infographic material:
 - a. Physical Materials
 - b. Area
 - c. Frequency
 - d. Time to post
 - e. Platforms to be used
 - f. Duration of posting
7. What criteria you considering in creating infographic materials for contactless Transaction?
 - a. In terms of Color
 - b. Shapes
 - c. Size
 - d. Text
 - e. Patterns/Plans
8. How do you ensure that the promotional/communication materials were able to catch the passenger's attention?
9. In your own perspective, why do you think this is the reason/s why there are still passengers that are Single Journey Tickets users given that you have initiatives to use Beep Card?
10. In your own perspective, what do you think is/are the barriers in communication with promoting contactless payment in passengers?
11. *Can I request for the copy of your posted public materials in the Stations and in the Social Media?*

Business Development

1. In your own perspective, what does the contactless transaction means? Where do you first know about it or Experienced it?
2. How does LRT-1/LRMC support the contactless initiatives in the railway industry in the Philippines?
3. What is the role of Business Development in terms of promotion of Ticket Vending Machine?
4. During the pandemic time, how does the Business Development plan for an alternative ticketing system to reduce the human-to-human interaction?
5. Are there any promotions on-going to maximize the use of Ticket Vending Machines or contactless transaction?
6. Is there a possibility in the future that LRT-1 will re-brand or update its design system in terms of Ticket Vending Machines?
7. What criteria/strategy does the Business Dev.-LRMC is considering in accepting partnerships from different organizations that would help to strengthen the contactless transaction?
 - a. How many partners that the LRMC have for the contactless Campaign?
8. How do you analyze the possible sales when partnering with an organization?
9. In your own perspective, why do you think this is the reason/s why there are still passengers that are Single Journey Tickets users given that you have initiatives to use Beep Card?
10. In your own perspective, what do you think is/are the barriers in communication with promoting contactless payment in passengers?

Station Operations

1. In your own perspective, what does the contactless transaction means?
2. How does LRT-1/LRMC support the contactless initiatives in the railway industry in the Philippines?
3. What is the role of Station Operations in terms of promotion of Ticket Vending Machine?
4. How do you promote Machine Learning to your passengers?
5. Are there any promotions on-going to maximize the use of Ticket Vending Machines or contactless transaction?
6. What are the strategies of your department to support the use of Ticket Vending Machines?
7. Comparing the campaign of the use of Ticket Vending Machine before and during the pandemic, how do you think the passengers adapted the system?
8. How do the Station Operations analyze or identify the needs or behavior of the passengers?
9. Aside from purchasing a ticket, does the TVM have other features?
10. Do you think the infographic materials/ promotions posted in the Station are easily catch the attention of the passengers?
11. During the pandemic time, how does the LRT-1 ensure that contactless transaction using TVM is safer than the usual vending process in Ticket booths?
12. In your own perspective, why do you think this is the reason/s why there are still passengers that are Single Journey Tickets users given that you have initiatives to use Beep Card?
13. In your own perspective, what do you think is/are the barriers in communication with promoting contactless payment in passengers?

ANNEX D

KEY INFORMANT INTERVIEW PHOTOS

